

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

**Energy AUDIT for 3 model apartments
And Photovoltaic Solar Panel simulations**

5 Reports contributing to
'Net-Zero transition for Post-Communist Urban Neighbourhoods in Tirana'

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ENERGY AUDIT REPORT

ENERGY EFFICIENCY REHABILITATION OF

OBJECT: *Building no.3, on 5th floor, Apartment no. 2*

PROJECT: *GreenFORCE - Foster Research Excellence for Green
Transition in the Western Balkans*

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ABBREVIATIONS

AKBN	National Agency of Natural Resources
AKPT	National Agency for Territorial Planning
AL	Albania
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineers
BMS	Building Management System
DCM	Decision Council Ministerial
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
ECM	Efficiency Component Measures
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measures
EN	European Norms
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPS	Expanded Polystyrene
ETICS	External thermal insulation compound system
EU	European Union
GFA	Gross Floor Area
GoA	Government of Albania
HDD	Heating degree days
IP	Inception Phase of Project
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol 1000-1:2010
MEI	Ministry of Energy and Industry
METDE	Ministry of Economic Development, Trade and Enterprise
MoM	Meeting of Minutes
MoT	Municipality of Tirana
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
P	The Project
RE	Renewable Energy
SYM	SymbioticA, Local Project Coordination Office of Consultant
ToR	Terms of Reference (from "Instructions to tenderers" by KfW)
TP	Technical Proposal
U	Coefficient of heat transmission
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
U_w	Coefficient of heat transmission of a window (including frame and glazing)
WB	Western Balkans
XPS	Extruded Polystyrene
λ	Thermal conductivity
€	Euro – Euro currency rate to AL Leke is taken 1€=100 Leke

TABLE OF UNITS

Description	Symbol	Measuring unit
Heat transfer coefficient	U	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Glass surface	Ag	[m ²]
Window frame surface	Af	[m ²]
Length of glass surface	Lg	[m]
Heat transfer from glass element	Kg	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Heat transfer from frame	Kf	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Linear heat transmission	Kl	[W/(m·K)]
Total heat transfer of frame	Kw	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Volume	Vol.	[m ³]
Wet thermometer temperature	Tdb	[°C]
Relative humidity	R.H.	[%]
Heat losses	H.L.	[W]
Feed rate	V	[m ³ /h]
Length	L	[m]
Net Surface	S	[m ²]
Increased security	Inc.	[%]
Temperature difference	ΔT	[K]

LAWS & STANDARDS

- REF. /1/ Law no. 124/2015 for energy efficiency
- REF. /2/ Law no. 116/2016 for the energy performance of buildings
- REF. /3/ Regulation no.5 dated 12.01.2021 for the energy audit form and
- REF. /4/ payment of the energy auditor.
- REF. /5/ DCM No. 1094 dated 24.12.2020 For the Approval of the National Methodology for calculating the performance of Energy in Buildings.
- REF. /6/ Decision no. 537, dated 8.7.2020 on the approval of the
- REF. /7/ minimum energy performance requirements of
- REF. /8/ buildings and building elements
- REF. /9/ Decision no. 480, dated 31.7.2018 for the approval of the national energy strategy for the period 2018–2030
- REF. /10/ Decision no. 958, dated 2.12.2020 for the approval of the procedures and
- REF. /11/ Conditions for the certification of the energy performance of buildings and the model, the content of the conditions for the registration of the "energy performance certificate of buildings"
- REF. /12/ Decision no.256, dated 27.3.2020 on the approval of the methodology for the calculation of optimal cost levels for the minimum energy performance requirements of buildings, units and building elements
- REF. /13/ Law NO.9379, dated 28.4.2005 "For Energy Efficiency"
- REF. /14/ Law no. 8937, dated 12.09.2002, On heat storage in buildings "
- REF. /15/ EN-ISO 10077 (2006) - Thermal transmission of windows, doors - Calculation of heat transfer
- REF. /16/ DIN V 18599-2: 2007-02 - Energy Efficiency in Buildings
- REF. /17/ EnEV 2014 - Energy Saving Rules
- REF. /18/ DCM No. 38, dated 16.01.2003, "On the approval of norms, rules and conditions of design and construction, production and storage of heat in buildings".
- REF. /19/ UNI EN 806 - "Specifications for indoor installations for water systems for human use"
- REF. /20/ EN ISO 13790 2008 "Thermal performance of buildings - Calculations for energy use for heating and cooling of premises";
- REF. /21/ EN- ISO 13789 (2007) "Thermal performance of buildings-Coefficients of heat transfer with transmission and ventilation, Calculation method";
- REF. /22/ EN-ISO 13370 (2007) - Thermal performance of the building - Heat transfer from the ground-Calculation method
- REF. /23/ EN-ISO 10456 (2007) - Building products and materials - Tables of values and procedures for determining the thermal values
- REF. /24/ EN-ISO 9251– Thermal Insulation - Conditions of heat transfer and characteristics of materials
- REF. /25/ EN ISO 7345- Thermal insulation - Physical quantities and definitions
- REF. /26/ EN-ISO 6946 (2007) - Building components and building elements - Thermal resistance and thermal transmission - Calculation method
- REF. /27/ DCM No. 853, dated 14.11.2007, "Use of compact fluorescent lamps
- REF. /28/ Directive 2012/27 / EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency
- REF. /29/ EN 15603 (2008) - Energy Performance of Buildings - General Energy Use and Definition of Energy Evaluation
- REF. /30/ EN 15459: 2006 - Energy efficiency in buildings - Standard economic evaluation procedures for energy systems in buildings

- REF. /31/ UNI 10339: 1995 - Air Conditioning Systems for Thermal Comfort in Buildings. General, classification and requirements. Offer, purpose and specifications of the supply
- REF. /32/ EN 15378 (2007) - Heating system of buildings – Inspection of boilers and heating systems
- REF. /33/ EN 15316 (2007) - Heating systems in buildings - Method of calculation of energy requirements of systems and efficiency of systems
- REF. /34/ EN 15239 (2007) - Ventilation of buildings - Energy performance of buildings - Guidelines for inspection of ventilation systems
- REF. /35/ EN 15193 (2007) - Energy performance of buildings - Energy requirements for lighting
- REF. /36/ REF. / 36 / DIN V 18599-10: 2007-02 - Energy efficiency in buildings - Calculation of energy needs, energy supplied, and primary energy for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting. - Part 10: Boundary conditions of use, climatic data
- REF. /37/ Technical Manuals DCM 27.06.2012. Official Journal 83-2012

1. INTRODUCTION

This report has been drafted in accordance with the Approved Regulation by stated on the Minister Order no.5 dated 12.01.2021 for the energy audit form and payment of the energy auditor. Article No. 4 of this regulation provides: Understanding and content of the Format of Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design as follows below:

- 1- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design is the document that defines the guideline to be implemented for energy auditors during the energy audit process for new buildings and buildings under design.
- 2- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design accompanies the energy performance certificate for new buildings or the preliminary energy performance certificate for buildings under design.
- 3- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design should contain a comparison between the elements considered during the design phase (their main / specific indicators on energy consumption and / or efficiency) and the issuance of the preliminary certificate and the elements of installed in the finished building according to appendix 2 attached to this instruction.

The audit report based on appendix No. 2 of this instruction of the above-mentioned Regulation shall contain at least the following elements described in detail of the buildings under design or new buildings.

1. Building envelop system

- a) Insulation
- b) Windows
- c) Air infiltrations $\Delta P = 50 \text{ Pa}$

2. Building Using Activity

3. Technical systems

- a) Heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning system
- b) Heat recovery systems
- c) Lighting systems
- d) Hot water sanitary systems

4. Energy management systems

- a) Control systems
- b) Measurement and verification systems

5. Use of alternative systems with high energy efficiency

- a) decentralized power supply systems utilizing renewable energy sources
- b) cogeneration systems, which realize the combined production of thermal energy and electrical or mechanical electricity
- c) systems with heat pumps, which change and transfer the natural flow of thermal energy, from the external environment to buildings or building units and conversely, if required
- d) Centralized heating and cooling systems, especially those that use renewable energy sources for buildings or building blocks.

Since the building under analysis is in the Design phase and will be subject to the process of obtaining a construction permit will be subject to Article 8 of Law 116/2016 For Energy Performance in Buildings,

the analysis of the possibility of using alternative systems with high energy efficiency should accompany the energy audit report for the buildings in the design phase.

2. PURPOSE OF ENERGY AUDIT

The energy audit consisted of:

- Audit of the physical construction of the building/premises.
- Audit of the heating system and domestic hot water system.
- Interviews with senior managers of the premises.
- Interrogation and discussions with the beneficiaries to obtain a typical user profile.
- Usage of relevant local climate data.

Methodology used included:

- Collection of basic information and data elaboration.
- Analyses and assessment of premises.
- Establishment of a data base for estimation of energy transmission in the premises.
- Elaboration of a consumption model for current use of energy.
- Simulation of processes for energy transmission and potential methods for energy savings.
- Establishing measures for energy savings and technical solutions.
- Technical and economic evaluation of measures for energy savings.

A detailed energy audit has been performed in line with the Terms of Reference and the Technical Proposal of the Consortium. This report is made in accordance with Albanian legislation [REF. /1/]. In addition, for a comprehensive report of the mentioned building and the systems that will be installed in it, have been used European Standards and Norms for “Energy Performance in Buildings”.

Below we will present some plans and section of the building according to the architecture project.

FIGURE 1: Plan of the apartment

FIGURE 2: The location of the apartment

FIGURE 3: Building section

FIGURE 4: Real photo of the object

FIGURE 5: Location of the object in google map

3. BUILDING USING ACTIVITY

The building under the study is located on the middle of the street: “Rruga Kongresi i Lushnjes” and street: “Rruga Ylberë Bylykbashi”, on the area “Kryqezimi 21 Dhjetori”, Tirana.

The main features and details of the building are summarized below:

- Building type: Residential building
- Owner: Private
- Gross surface of the building: 55 m²

Summarized the condition of the buildings can be stated as follows:

- Walls are not insulated.
- Windows are single glazed with not insulated frames.
- Extensive mould occurs due to heat bridge effects.
- Roofs are not thermo-insulated, and the hydro-isolation is partly leaking.
- The Electrical System is old and in very poor condition.
- The Heating System is inefficient regarding to the new equipment’s generation and standards for SEER and COP.
- The electric boiler for the domestic hot water production is old and worn out. Their performance is not good.
- Thermal comfort is very poor especially during winter.

TABLE 1: General building details

Building details		
Date of construction (year)	between 1970-1985	
Gross surface of the building	55 m ²	
Net surface of the building	48 m ²	
Volume of the building	154 m ³	(approximately)
Dimensions of the building	A = 7.3 m	
	B = 10 m	
	H = 2.8 m	
Number of floors	1	
Number of rooms	4	
Terrace surface	55 m ²	
Surface of the walls	96 m ²	
Door/ Window Surface	7.2 m ²	
Floor surface	55 m ²	

4. BUILDING ENVELOPE SYSTEM – *current situation*

Below will be analysed the covered structured of the building, thermal analysis and the compliance with the Albanian Legislation in force. This building is designed with supporting structure reinforced concrete pile foundations, prefabricated concrete walls, monolithic terrace.

4.1. Insulation

4.1.1 Structure of the Exterior Wall of the building

The external walls of the building are prefabricated concrete slabs with a thickness of 20 cm, installation without any insulating layers.

FIGURE 6: Exterior wall structure

TABLE 2: U-value, Structure of external surrounding wall

Description: Exterior wall						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W			0.123	
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)			0.043	
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.488					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Light weight concrete	12	0.29	2.4		800	0.41
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1,800	0.02
The sum of the resistances (R)						0.672

Referring to the preliminary information for the exterior wall layers, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.488 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” for existing buildings when they undergo a significant renovation, is in value 0.40 (W/m²K), the surrounding walls of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.2 Structure of the floor

FIGURE 7: Floor structure

TABLE 3: U-value, Floor structure

Description: Floor						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W			0.110	
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)			0.043	
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.650					
LAYERS						
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	Thermal Resistance
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to outside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Reinforced concrete	15	1.16	7.7	1	2000	0.13
Lightweight concrete screed	8	0.35	4.4		1000	0.23
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
Water proofing layer	1	0.26	26.0		1300	0.04
Tiles adhesive	1	0.9	90.0		1800	0.01
Porcelain tiles	2	1	50.0		2300	0.02
The sum of the resistances						0.606

Referring to preliminary information for floor coverings, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.650 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” which is in value 0.45 (W/m²K), the floor of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.3 Terrace structure

FIGURE 8: Terrace structure

TABLE 4: U-value, Terrace structure

Description: Roof						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W			0.110	
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)			0.043	
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.731					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to outside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Reinforced concrete	15	1.16	7.7	1	2000	0.13
Lightweight concrete screed	8	0.35	4.4		1000	0.23
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
Water proofing layer	1	0.26	26.0		1300	0.04
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
The sum of the resistances						0.578

Referring to preliminary information for roof coverings, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.731 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” which is iv value 0.35 (W/m²K), the covering structure of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.1 Other coefficients of the internal structures of the building

FIGURE 9: Interior wall structure

TABLE 5: U-value, Interior wall structure

Description: Interior brick wall						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W			0.123	
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)			0.123	
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.455					
LAYERS						
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	Thermal Resistance
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Exterior cement plaster	2.5	0.9	36.0	0.91	1,800	0.03
Silicate brick wall	20	0.52	2.6	0.88	1,200	0.38
Gypsum plaster	2.5	0.9	36.0	0.91	1,800	0.03
The sum of the resistances (R)						0.687

5. TECHNICAL SYSTEMS

5.1.1 Heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning system

Cooling and Heating System

Efficiency demands a new rating system for heating and cooling products, which must be used by all manufacturers. These are:

- The Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) value in cooling
- The Coefficient of Performance (COP) value in heating

According to directive 2012/27/EU, products used for room air conditioning must meet minimum energy efficiency requirements.

The selected cooling and heating system for this building is a split type, using the eco-friendly refrigerant R410a. Our appliance is class B, the Energy Efficiency Ratio is EER=3.1 and the Coefficient of Performance) is COP=3.3 which are greater from the above-mentioned minimum values.

TABLE 6: Present Heating/cooling system consumption

Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Heating/cooling capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Single-split air conditioner	3.4/3.2kW	2	1,200.00	2.4	6	14.4	5,256.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m ² a)							95.56

FIGURE 10: EER / COP annual energy consumption and efficiency (directive 2012/27/EU)

Ventilation System

There is no mechanical or forced ventilation system installed in this apartment. Currently the air exchange in the rooms is provided accidentally by excessive air infiltration through bad quality doors and windows. Additionally, the inappropriate user behaviour (reacting to the bad building and comfort conditions) also influences the room ventilation: by leaving the doors and windows opened or closed for a long period, the following consequences can be observed:

1. High energy consumption to keep a bearable temperature (warmer or cooler) for all spaces.
2. No sufficient room ventilation can be achieved, especially in winter times.

The lack of ventilation becomes obvious in the toilet where we face the presence of mould.

5.1.2 Lighting systems

The lighting system that is used in the apartment is by fluorescent lights will high efficiency and low energy consumption luminaires with a minimum output of 58 lm / Watt efficiency.

FIGURE 11: Lumens per watt (lm/W) explained

TABLE 7: Present lighting consumption

Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting before EEM							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	Incandescent	1	65	0.065	12	0.78	284.70
Living room	Incandescent	2	65	0.13	12	1.56	569.40
Toilet	fluorescent	2	32	0.064	12	0.768	280.32
Bedroom	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Corridor	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Balcony	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Total				0.411		4.932	1,940.34
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							35.28

Minimum comfort requirements

TABLE 8: Comfort lighting levels for different typologies of residential building areas

Area typology (code)	Name of the area	Lighting ² (lux)
R&JR	Bedroom	125
	Living room	150
	Kitchen	200
	Bathroom/WC, with shower	100
	Corridor/staircase	100

²The technical requirements, the main terms for the lighting of buildings and the basic norms of lighting design are defined in the Standard SSH EN 12464-1:2011, "Light and lighting", approved by the General Directorate of Standards, as an Albanian standard on 2012.12.20.

5.1.3 Hot water sanitary systems

In the specific building is required low demand in hot water for use. Therefore, a local electrical water heater is installed, 2.5 kW power, 100 Liters of storage capacity, suitable to satisfy the needs of its users.

FIGURE 12: Electric boiler for hot water

TABLE 9: Present Sanitary hot water consumption

Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise before EEM							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	2,500.00	2.5	12	30	10,950.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m ² a)							199.09

6. THERMAL LOSS CALCULATIONS

6.1 Thermal loss of the building

Building data

Average minimum outside temperature	0°C
Desired indoor temperature	21°C
Non heated spaces temperature	10°C
Soil temperature	10°C
Calculation method	DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003
Unit system	Watt

The following calculations show the heat transfer in the winter period.

TABLE 10: Heat losses in the winter period in actual conditions (referring to the table no.9)

Heat losses from building envelope (Watt)							
Air infiltrations	Floor	Terrace	Walls	Doors and Windows	Thermal node	Correction factor	Total heat losses (W)
3,201.7	272.3	1,999.3	1,112.8	873.7	404.0	943.6	8,807.3

TABLE 11: Heat losses calculation of the building

HEAT LOSSES CALCULATIONS OF THE BUILDING																		
Structures	Volume of heating spaces	ORIENTATION	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Length	Height	Surface	Surface which need to be deduced	The outer surface of the structure	Desired indoor temperature (tb)	Outside temperature (ti)	Heat losses (Qt)	Heat losses in the nodes (Qn)	Heat losses (Orientation supplements)		Heat losses from the air infiltrations		Total heat losses	
	m3		W/m²·K	m	m	m²	m²	m²	°C	°C	W	W	%	W	naj	W	W	
Exterior wall	154.0	N	1.488	7.30	2.80	20.44	2.4	18.01	21	0	562.8	56.3	20	112.6	3	3201.7	731.6	
Exterior wall		S	1.488	3.46	2.80	9.69	2.3	7.44	21	0	232.4	23.2	0	0.0			255.7	
Interior wall		E	1.455	4.90	2.80	13.72	0.0	13.72	21	18	59.9	6.0	10	6.0			71.9	
Interior wall		W	1.455	9.90	2.80	27.72	0.0	27.72	21	18	121.0	12.1	15	18.1			151.2	
Window		N	7.000	2.70	0.90	2.43	0.0	2.43	21	0	357.2	35.7	20	71.4			464.4	
Window		S	7.000	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	330.8	33.1	0	0.0			363.8	
Exterior door		E	2.5	0.90	2.20	1.98	0.0	1.98	21	0	104.0	10.4	10	10.4			124.7	
Floor				1.650	-	-	55.00	0.0	55.00	21	18	272.3	27.2	0			0.0	299.5
Terrace				1.731	-	-	55.00	0.0	55.00	21	0	1999.3	199.9	0			0.0	2,199.2
															Qtot	7,863.7	W	
															Gv	1.44	W/m³°C	
SURFACE 55 M2						Corrections in percentage (%) for intermittent operation and load reduction											943.6	W
						Continued use with reduction at night - Plant with warm air 12%												
S/V=	0.36																8,807.3	W

6.1 Calculation of the volume heat loss coefficient G_{vt} ($W/m^3\text{°C}$)

Referring to the Building Energy Code and DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 “For the approval of norms, rules and conditions of design and construction, production and storage of heat in buildings”, calculation of the volume heat loss coefficient G_{vt} ($W/m^3\text{°C}$), is done as below:

$$G_{vt} = \frac{Q_0}{V * \Delta t} \quad (1)$$

where:

- G_{vt} - Coefficient of volume heat loss ($W/m^3\text{°C}$);
- Q_0 - Heat losses from the envelope;
- V - Building volume;
- t_b - Desired indoor temperature (21°C);
- t_j - Outside temperature (0°C).

For our building the report S/V is as below:

$$\frac{S}{V} = 0.36 \quad (2)$$

where:

- S - The outer surface of the structure 55 m^2
- V - Volume of heating spaces 154 m^3

For our building we can calculate: $G_{vt} = 2.723\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$

Below table show the value of the G_{vt} (S/V report) for the building envelope based on the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003.

TABLE 12: Normative value of the volume heat loss coefficient though transmission G_{vt0}

S/V	ZONES ACCORDING TO THE GRADE DAYS					
	A		B		C	
	grade day 900 ÷ 1500		grade day 1501 ÷ 2500		grade day 2501 ÷ 3000	
≤ 0.3	0.62	0.54	0.54	0.45	0.45	0.41
≥ 0.9	1.20	1.03	1.03	0.86	0.86	0.81

Tirana region is located at climatic zone A, with 1173 Grade Days. Based on above table, part of the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 through interpolation we derive that for the report $\frac{S}{V} = 0.36$ of our building, the normative coefficient for the allow volume heat loss its $G_{vt0} = 1.58\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

From heat losses calculation shown in above table, the volume heat loss coefficient with transmission for the building analysed is $G_{vt} = 2.723\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

In our case: $G_{vt} > G_{vt0}$

As conclusion we can state that analyses building doesn't fulfils the Albanian legal requirements for the heat losses in the building.

Note: G_{v_i} is higher than $G_{v_{to}}$ which is against the condition recommended by the DCM No..38.

6.2 Calculation of the energy consumption for the heating

Needed heating energy for the building is calculated as below:

$$E_{\text{vijetore}} = \frac{Q_0 * Grd * h / dite}{\Delta t}$$

where:

- Q_0 - Heat losses from the envelope Wat;
- Grd - heating grade days (1,173);
- h/day - Number of the hours used for the heating of the building (6 hours);
- Δt - Design temperature difference (21°C).

TABLE 13: Annual energy consumption for heating before EEM

Annual energy consumption			
No.	Description	Value	Unit
1	Heat losses	8,807.3	Wat
2	Plant operating time (Continued use with reduction at night)	6	hour
3	Grade day	1,534	GRD
4	Design temperature difference	21.00	°C
5	Building surface	55.00	m ²
6	Annual thermal energy	3,860.13	kWh/a
	Annual specific consumption	70.18	kWh/m²a

As can be seen from the table above, based on the relevant data and calculations, the annual energy demand for heating of the building under analysis will be **3,860.13 kWh/a**, with a specific consumption of **70.18 kWh/ m²a**.

7. CURRENT ENERGETIC CLASSIFICATION OF THE APARTMENT

The measured energy consumption is not representative according to modern standards and comfort conditions. As there is currently no Albanian standard (fixing comfort requirements for lighting, hot sanitary water and heating) available the German ENEC standard was used to calculate the energy consumption baseline including comfort conditions.

The specific energy consumption of the building in the baseline case is **70.18 kWh/(m²a)**. Compared to the reference building defined in the German code the energy consumption of the present building is 128% higher.

Compared to the Albanian Law for Energy Efficiency in buildings this value does not meets the minimum requirements of this standard.

FIGURE 13: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the reference building

FIGURE 14: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the Albanian Law

8. MEASURES FOR INCREASING THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY CLASS

Energy efficiency describes the ratio between the benefit obtained and the energy used. From an economic point of view, energy efficiency can be described as the marginal productivity of energy input, specifying how much energy is needed to produce a given level of output (heat, light, motion, comfort).

FIGURE 15: Heat losses in a building from the envelope system

Main energy saving measures

- Insulation of walls and roofs/terraces
- Installation of energy efficient windows
- Installation of an energy efficient heating system
- Installation of an energy efficient cooling system
- Use of energy-efficient electric heaters
- Use of solar water heating systems
- Installation of an efficient lighting system
- Purchase of efficient household appliances

Below are the U values for the building structures according to the Decision No. 537, date 8.7.2020

TABLE 14: Comparison of U values for building structures

Building covering elements	Value U calculated (W/m ² K)	Comments	Maximum allowable U value as defined in the regulation U max (W/m ² K)	Legal basis
Exterior walls	1.488	Should be improved	0.40	DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020
Terrace	1.731	Should be improved	0.35	
Floor	1.650	In this case the floor is bounded by a heated room not based on the ground	0.45	
Windows	7.00	Should be improved	2.20	

According to this Decision we can prove that all the U values calculated for this apartment are higher than the maximum allowable, so we must act on improvement of all building covering elements by reconfiguring the layers to improve the performance of envelope system.

8.1.1 Exterior wall insulation

Insulation of the exterior walls should be provided in case of reducing the value of the building heat loss in the heating and cooling conditions.

FIGURE 16: External wall insulation layers

TABLE 15: U-value, Exterior wall structure – proposed

Description: Exterior wall - Proposed						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² °C/W		0.123		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² °C/W)		0.043		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	0.386					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² °C/W]
EIFS plaster	2.5	0.79	31.6		1,600	0.03
Insulation board + adhesive + reinforcing mesh	8	0.039	0.5		20	2.05
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Light weight concrete	12	0.29	2.4		800	0.41
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1,800	0.02
The sum of the resistances (R)						2.588

FIGURE 17: Comparison of heat transmission coefficients for different thicknesses

8.1.1 Terrace insulation

Insulation of the terrace should be provided, and it is necessary to obtain the minimum allowable U value.

TABLE 16: U-value, Terrace structure – proposed

Description: Terrace proposed						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m²·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ²⁰ C/W	0.110			
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m²·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ²⁰ C/W)	0.043			
Coefficient U [W/(m²·K)]:	0.318					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to outside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m²·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m³]	[m ²⁰ C/W]
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Reinforced concrete	15	1.16	7.7	1	2000	0.13
Lightweight concrete screed	8	0.35	4.4		1000	0.23
Insulation board XPS	10	0.039	0.4		20	2.56
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
Water proofing layer	1	0.26	26.0		1300	0.04
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
The sum of the resistances						3.142

8.1.1 Floor insulation

TABLE 17: U-value, Floor structure – proposed

Description: Floor - Proposed						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² 0C/W	0.110			
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² 0C/W)	0.043			
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	0.811					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² 0C/W]
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Reinforced concrete	15	1.16	7.7	1	2000	0.13
Lightweight concrete screed	12	0.35	2.9		1000	0.34
Insulation board XPS	2	0.039	2.0		20	0.51
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
Water proofing layer	1	0.26	26.0		1300	0.04
Tiles adhesive	1	0.9	90.0		1800	0.01
Porcelain tiles	2	1	50.0		2300	0.02
The sum of the resistances						1.233

8.1.2 Replacing Windows, Reducing the K coefficient

The windows in the apartment consist of none insulated aluminium frames with single glazed sliding panels. The thermal quality therefore is very poor. In conclusion, the improvement/replacement of the windows will be done for all apartment, in case to reduce the monthly bill (these windows with such elements reduce the infiltration of air and the loss of solar heat, reducing the amount of energy for heating and cooling the building).

Another small improvement can be the use of warm plastic spacers joining the glass pane instead of the typical aluminium option. The size of the gap between the glass is important too. Best windows offer 18mm space in the triple-glazed version and 24mm in double-glazed windows.

FIGURE 18: Single pane, double pane and triple pane glass window

TABLE 19

Overall U-factors (heat transfer coefficients) for various windows and skylights in $W/m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$ (from ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamentals, Chap. 27, Table 5)

Type	Glass section (glazing) only			Aluminum frame (without thermal break)			Wood or vinyl frame					
	Center-of-glass	Edge-of-glass		Fixed	Double door	Sloped skylight	Fixed	Double door		Sloped skylight		
Frame width →	(Not applicable)			32 mm (1¼ in)	53 mm (2 in)	19 mm (¾ in)	41 mm (1½ in)	88 mm (3½ in)		23 mm (¾ in)		
Spacer type →	—	Metal	Insul.	All	All	All	Metal	Insul.	Metal	Insul.	Metal	Insul.
Glazing Type												
Single Glazing												
3 mm (¼ in) glass	6.30	6.30	—	6.63	7.16	9.88	5.93	—	5.57	—	7.57	—
6.4 mm (¼ in) acrylic	5.28	5.28	—	5.69	6.27	8.86	5.02	—	4.77	—	6.57	—
3 mm (¼ in) acrylic	5.79	5.79	—	6.16	6.71	9.94	5.48	—	5.17	—	7.63	—
Double Glazing (no coating)												
6.4 mm air space	3.24	3.71	3.34	3.90	4.55	6.70	3.26	3.16	3.20	3.09	4.37	4.22
12.7 mm air space	2.78	3.40	2.91	3.51	4.18	6.65	2.88	2.76	2.86	2.74	4.32	4.17
6.4 mm argon space	2.95	3.52	3.07	3.66	4.32	6.47	3.03	2.91	2.98	2.87	4.14	3.97
12.7 mm argon space	2.61	3.28	2.76	3.36	4.04	6.47	2.74	2.61	2.73	2.60	4.14	3.97
Double Glazing [$\epsilon = 0.1$, coating on one of the surfaces of air space (surface 2 or 3, counting from the outside toward inside)]												
6.4 mm air space	2.44	3.16	2.60	3.21	3.89	6.04	2.59	2.46	2.60	2.47	3.73	3.53
12.7 mm air space	1.82	2.71	2.06	2.67	3.37	6.04	2.06	1.92	2.13	1.99	3.73	3.53
6.4 mm argon space	1.99	2.83	2.21	2.82	3.52	5.62	2.21	2.07	2.26	2.12	3.32	3.09
12.7 mm argon space	1.53	2.49	1.83	2.42	3.14	5.71	1.82	1.67	1.91	1.78	3.41	3.19
Triple Glazing (no coating)												
6.4 mm air space	2.16	2.96	2.35	2.97	3.66	5.81	2.34	2.18	2.36	2.21	3.48	3.24
12.7 mm air space	1.76	2.67	2.02	2.62	3.33	5.67	2.01	1.84	2.07	1.91	3.34	3.09
6.4 mm argon space	1.93	2.79	2.16	2.77	3.47	5.57	2.15	1.99	2.19	2.04	3.25	3.00
12.7 mm argon space	1.65	2.58	1.92	2.52	3.23	5.53	1.91	1.74	1.98	1.82	3.20	2.95
Triple Glazing [$\epsilon = 0.1$, coating on one of the surfaces of air spaces (surfaces 3 and 5, counting from the outside toward inside)]												
6.4 mm air space	1.53	2.49	1.83	2.42	3.14	5.24	1.81	1.64	1.89	1.73	2.92	2.66
12.7 mm air space	0.97	2.05	1.38	1.92	2.66	5.10	1.33	1.15	1.46	1.30	2.78	2.52
6.4 mm argon space	1.19	2.23	1.56	2.12	2.85	4.90	1.52	1.35	1.64	1.47	2.59	2.33
12.7 mm argon space	0.80	1.92	1.25	1.77	2.51	4.86	1.18	1.01	1.33	1.17	2.55	2.28

TABLE 18: Overall U-value for various windows (according to ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamentals)

The type of window that we have selected for the replacement of the old ones is the one significant in the red square.

8.1.3 Replacing the lighting system

The following measures are recommended:

- Replacing the incandescent and fluorescent lamps (CFL) currently installed with LED lamps ensuring also the actual required illumination value.

FIGURE 19: Energy saving vs Energy consumption on lighting systems

8.1.4 Increasing the efficiency of the heating/cooling system

The new system selected for heating and cooling this apartment must belong to class A of energy efficiency, with the Energy Efficiency Ratio EER > 3.2 and the Coefficient of Performance COP > 3.6.

9. THERMAL LOSS CALCULATIONS

TABLE 19: Heat losses in the winter period after AEE (referring to the table no.19)

Heat losses from building envelope after AEE(Wat)							
Air infiltrations	Floor	Terrace	Walls	Doors and Windows	Thermal node	Correction factor	Total heat losses (W)
3,201.7	133.8	367.3	440.5	197.9	106.8	533.8	4,981.7

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TABLE 20: Heat losses calculation of the building after EEM

HEAT LOSSES CALCULATIONS OF THE BUILDING AFTER EEM																		
Structures	Volume of heating spaces	ORIENTATION	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Length	Height	Surface	Surface which need to be deduced	The outer surface of the structure	Desired indoor temperature (tb)	Outside temperature (ti)	Heat losses (Qt)	Heat losses in the nodes (Qt)	Heat losses (Orientation supplements)		Heat losses from the air infiltrations		Total heat losses	
	m3		W/m ² ·K	m	m	m ²	m ²	m ²	°C	°C	W	W	%	W	naj	W	W	
Exterior wall	154.0	N	0.386	7.30	2.80	20.44	2.4	18.01	21	0	146.0	14.6	20	29.2	3	3201.7	189.8	
Exterior wall		S	0.386	3.46	2.80	9.69	2.3	7.44	21	0	60.3	6.0	0	0.0			66.3	
Interior wall		E	1.455	4.90	2.80	13.72	0.0	13.72	21	18	59.9	6.0	10	6.0			71.9	
Interior wall		W	1.455	9.90	2.80	27.72	0.0	27.72	21	18	121.0	12.1	15	18.1			151.2	
Window		N	1.150	2.70	0.90	2.43	0.0	2.43	21	0	58.7	5.9	20	11.7			76.3	
Window		S	1.150	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	54.3	5.4	0	0.0			59.8	
Exterior door		E	1.6	0.90	2.20	1.98	0.0	1.98	21	0	66.5	6.7	10	6.7			79.8	
Floor				0.811	-	-	55.00	0.0	55.00	21	18	133.8	13.4	0			0.0	147.2
Terrace				0.318	-	-	55.00	0.0	55.00	21	0	367.3	36.7	0			0.0	404.0
															Qtot	4,448.0	W	
															Gv	0.39	W/m ³ °C	
SURFACE 55 M2							Corrections in persentage (%) for intermittent operation and load reduction										533.8	W
							Continued use with reduction at night - Plant with warm air 12%											
S/V=	0.36															4,981.7	W	

Based on the previous information's, part of the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 through interpolation we derive that for the report $\frac{S}{V} = 0.36$ of our building is the same as before, the normative coefficient for the allow volume heat loss its $G_{vt0} = 1.58 \text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

From heat losses calculation shown in above table, the new volume heat loss coefficient with transmission for the building analysed is $G_{vt} = 1.540 \text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

In our case: $G_{vt} \leq G_{vt0}$

As conclusion we can state that analyses building after EEM fulfils the Albanian legal requirements for the heat losses in the building.

Note: G_{vt} is lower than G_{vt0} which is conform the condition recommended by the DCM No..38.

10. ENERGETIC CLASSIFICATION OF THE APARTMENT AFTER EEM

TABLE 21: Annual energy consumption for heating before EEM

Annual energy consumption			
No.	Description	Value	Unit
1	Heat losses	4,981.7	Wat
2	Plant operating time (Continued use with reduction at night)	6	hour
3	Grade day	1,534	GRD
4	Design temperature difference	21.00	°C
5	Building surface	55.00	m ²
6	Annual thermal energy	2,183.43	kWh/a
	Annual specific consumption	39.70	kWh/m²a

FIGURE 20: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the new building conditions

FIGURE 21: Classification of Energy Class regarding to the Albanian Law

11. COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

The estimated costs of the structural and comfort measures are based on official cost tables provided by the Ministry of Transport & Infrastructure¹ and on Albanian market prices.

The costs are estimated for the structural measures which are fundamental and should be realized before or in combination with further energy efficiency measures.

TABLE 22: Electrical consumption and costs before EEM

Electrical consumption before EEM							
Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	Incandescent	1	65	0.065	12	0.78	284.70
Living room	Incandescent	2	65	0.13	12	1.56	569.40
Toilet	fluorescent	2	32	0.064	12	0.768	280.32
Bedroom	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Corridor	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Balcony	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Total				0.411		4.932	1,940.34
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							35.28
Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Heating/cooling capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Single-split air conditioner	3.4/3.2 kW	2	1,200.00	2.4	6	14.4	5,256.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							95.56
Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	2,500.00	2.5	12	30	10,950.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							199.09
ELECTRICAL COST							
Total Electrical Annual consumption (kWh/a)							18,146.34
The price of electricity (euro/kWh)							0.14
Total price of Electrical Annual consumption before EEM(euro)							2,540.49

¹ REF. [28] Technical Manuals MD 2012, Official Bulletin 83- 2012, <http://www.mppt.gov.al/>

TABLE 23: Electrical consumption and costs after EEM

Electrical consumption after EEM							
Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (k Wh/d)	Annual consumption (k Wh/a)
Kitchen	LED	1	20	0.02	12	0.24	87.60
Living room	LED	1	30	0.03	12	0.36	131.40
Toilet	LED	1	10	0.01	12	0.12	43.80
Bedroom	LED	1	15	0.015	12	0.18	65.70
Corridor	LED	1	10	0.01	12	0.12	43.80
Balcony	LED	1	5	0.005	12	0.06	21.90
Total				0.085		1.02	394.20
Specific electrical energy (k Wh/m ² a)							7.17
Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Annual consumption (kWh/a)			COP		Annual consumption (k Wh/a)	
Single-split air conditioner	4,366.9			3.8		1,149.17	
Specific electrical energy (k Wh/m ² a)							20.89
Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (k Wh/d)	Annual consumption (k Wh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	1,200.00	1.2	12	14.4	5,256.00
Specific electrical energy (k Wh/m ² a)							95.56
ELECTRICAL COST							
Total Electrical Annual consumption (kWh/a)							6,799.37
The price of electricity (euro/k Wh)							0.14
Total price of Electrical Annual consumption after EEM (euro)							951.91

TABLE 24: Total investment value for EEM

Building Envelope Measures	Unit	Qty	Unit price [€]	Investment Cost [€]
Preparation for the EE Measures (demolition, transportation, cleaning up)	m2	55.00	10 €	550.00 €
External wall envelope (thermal insulation EPS thickness 8 cm)	m2	25.45	25.00 €	636.25 €
Roof layers (thermal insulation XPS thickness 10 cm)	m2	55.00	28.00 €	1,540.00 €
Windows Renewal ≤ 1.4 W/m ² K	m2	4.68	140.00 €	655.20 €
Thermo-insulation of the Floor (XPS thickness 3 cm)	m3	1.65	100.00 €	165.00 €
Lightweight concrete screed for floor (3 cm layer)	m3	1.65	110.00 €	181.50 €
Laminat e floor 0.8 cm	m2	55.00	15.00 €	825.00 €
TOTAL COSTS 1 (€)				4,552.95 €
Other EE Measures	Unit	Qty	Unit price [€]	Investment Cost [€]
Heating/cooling Air Condition system	pcs	2.00	650 €	1,300 €
DHW: 50% Solar Thermal Panels + 50% Air Heat Pumps	pcs	-	-	1,250.00 €
Photovoltaic panels	pcs	-	-	1,470.00 €
Lighting (CFL + LED)	pcs	6.00	80 €	480 €
TOTAL COSTS 2 (€)				4,500.00 €
TOTAL COSTS without Solar and photovoltaic panels [1+2] (€)				6,332.95 €
TOTAL COSTS with Solar and photovoltaic panels [1+2] (€)				9,052.95 €

TABLE 25: Savings and investment repayment time

Total cost of Electrical Annual consumption before EEM (euro)	Total cost of Electrical Annual consumption after EEM (euro)	Annual savings (euro)	Total Investment value (euro)	Payback period (years)
2,540.49 €	951.91 €	1,588.58 €	6,332.95 €	4.0

12. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Analysis done for the baseline show that the apartment taken in analyse has an energy consumption of **70.18 kWh/m²a**, classifying in **ENERGY CLASSES C**, which according to the **Albanian law (*Law no. 116 date 10.11.2016 for Energy Efficiency in Buildings*)**.

In based of such analysis its recommended to be done some interventions which will bring the apartment **39.70 kWh/m²a**, in **ENERGY CLASSES B**, fulfilling the requirements of Albanian law.

Needed interventions:

- Insulation for the entire building envelope
- Replacing the lighting system from CFL and Incandescent lights to LED
- Replacing the electric boiler from standard on/off to smart boilers that saves up to 20% energy
- Replacement of the old mono-split heating/cooling non inverter to new equipment's with higher performance and inverter

Further recommendations for increasing the **ENERGY CLASSES** from **B** to **A**:

- Replacing the electric boilers with solar panels for generating hot sanitary water
- Installation of photovoltaic panels to save electrical energy and use of its energy for heating/cooling system.

ENERGY AUDIT REPORT

ENERGY EFFICIENCY REHABILITATION OF

OBJECT: *Building no.4, on ground floor, Apartment no. 3*

PROJECT: *GreenFORCE - Foster Research Excellence for Green
Transition in the Western Balkans*

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ABBREVIATIONS

AKBN	National Agency of Natural Resources
AKPT	National Agency for Territorial Planning
AL	Albania
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineers
BMS	Building Management System
DCM	Decision Council Ministerial
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
ECM	Efficiency Component Measures
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measures
EN	European Norms
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPS	Expanded Polystyrene
ETICS	External thermal insulation compound system
EU	European Union
GFA	Gross Floor Area
GoA	Government of Albania
HDD	Heating degree days
IP	Inception Phase of Project
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol 1000-1:2010
MEI	Ministry of Energy and Industry
METDE	Ministry of Economic Development, Trade and Enterprise
MoM	Meeting of Minutes
MoT	Municipality of Tirana
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
P	The Project
RE	Renewable Energy
SYM	SymbioticA, Local Project Coordination Office of Consultant
ToR	Terms of Reference (from "Instructions to tenderers" by KfW)
TP	Technical Proposal
U	Coefficient of heat transmission
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
U_w	Coefficient of heat transmission of a window (including frame and glazing)
WB	Western Balkans
XPS	Extruded Polystyrene
λ	Thermal conductivity
€	Euro – Euro currency rate to AL Leke is taken 1€=100 Leke

TABLE OF UNITS

Description	Symbol	Measuring unit
Heat transfer coefficient	U	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Glass surface	Ag	[m ²]
Window frame surface	Af	[m ²]
Length of glass surface	Lg	[m]
Heat transfer from glass element	Kg	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Heat transfer from frame	Kf	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Linear heat transmission	Kl	[W/(m·K)]
Total heat transfer of frame	Kw	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Volume	Vol.	[m ³]
Wet thermometer temperature	Tdb	[°C]
Relative humidity	R.H.	[%]
Heat losses	H.L.	[W]
Feed rate	V	[m ³ /h]
Length	L	[m]
Net Surface	S	[m ²]
Increased security	Inc.	[%]
Temperature difference	ΔT	[K]

LAWS & STANDARDS

- REF. /1/ Law no. 124/2015 for energy efficiency
- REF. /2/ Law no. 116/2016 for the energy performance of buildings
- REF. /3/ Regulation no.5 dated 12.01.2021 for the energy audit form and
- REF. /4/ payment of the energy auditor.
- REF. /5/ DCM No. 1094 dated 24.12.2020 For the Approval of the National Methodology for calculating the performance of Energy in Buildings.
- REF. /6/ Decision no. 537, dated 8.7.2020 on the approval of the
- REF. /7/ minimum energy performance requirements of
- REF. /8/ buildings and building elements
- REF. /9/ Decision no. 480, dated 31.7.2018 for the approval of the national energy strategy for the period 2018–2030
- REF. /10/ Decision no. 958, dated 2.12.2020 for the approval of the procedures and
- REF. /11/ Conditions for the certification of the energy performance of buildings and the model, the content of the conditions for the registration of the "energy performance certificate of buildings"
- REF. /12/ Decision no.256, dated 27.3.2020 on the approval of the methodology for the calculation of optimal cost levels for the minimum energy performance requirements of buildings, units and building elements
- REF. /13/ Law NO.9379, dated 28.4.2005 "For Energy Efficiency"
- REF. /14/ Law no. 8937, dated 12.09.2002, On heat storage in buildings "
- REF. /15/ EN-ISO 10077 (2006) - Thermal transmission of windows, doors - Calculation of heat transfer
- REF. /16/ DIN V 18599-2: 2007-02 - Energy Efficiency in Buildings
- REF. /17/ EnEV 2014 - Energy Saving Rules
- REF. /18/ DCM No. 38, dated 16.01.2003, "On the approval of norms, rules and conditions of design and construction, production and storage of heat in buildings".
- REF. /19/ UNI EN 806 - "Specifications for indoor installations for water systems for human use"
- REF. /20/ EN ISO 13790 2008 "Thermal performance of buildings - Calculations for energy use for heating and cooling of premises";
- REF. /21/ EN- ISO 13789 (2007) "Thermal performance of buildings-Coefficients of heat transfer with transmission and ventilation, Calculation method";
- REF. /22/ EN-ISO 13370 (2007) - Thermal performance of the building - Heat transfer from the ground-Calculation method
- REF. /23/ EN-ISO 10456 (2007) - Building products and materials - Tables of values and procedures for determining the thermal values
- REF. /24/ EN-ISO 9251– Thermal Insulation - Conditions of heat transfer and characteristics of materials
- REF. /25/ EN ISO 7345- Thermal insulation - Physical quantities and definitions
- REF. /26/ EN-ISO 6946 (2007) - Building components and building elements - Thermal resistance and thermal transmission - Calculation method
- REF. /27/ DCM No. 853, dated 14.11.2007, "Use of compact fluorescent lamps
- REF. /28/ Directive 2012/27 / EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency
- REF. /29/ EN 15603 (2008) - Energy Performance of Buildings - General Energy Use and Definition of Energy Evaluation
- REF. /30/ EN 15459: 2006 - Energy efficiency in buildings - Standard economic evaluation procedures for energy systems in buildings

- REF. /31/ UNI 10339: 1995 - Air Conditioning Systems for Thermal Comfort in Buildings. General, classification and requirements. Offer, purpose and specifications of the supply
- REF. /32/ EN 15378 (2007) - Heating system of buildings – Inspection of boilers and heating systems
- REF. /33/ EN 15316 (2007) - Heating systems in buildings - Method of calculation of energy requirements of systems and efficiency of systems
- REF. /34/ EN 15239 (2007) - Ventilation of buildings - Energy performance of buildings - Guidelines for inspection of ventilation systems
- REF. /35/ EN 15193 (2007) - Energy performance of buildings - Energy requirements for lighting
- REF. /36/ REF. / 36 / DIN V 18599-10: 2007-02 - Energy efficiency in buildings - Calculation of energy needs, energy supplied, and primary energy for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting. - Part 10: Boundary conditions of use, climatic data
- REF. /37/ Technical Manuals DCM 27.06.2012. Official Journal 83-2012

1. INTRODUCTION

This report has been drafted in accordance with the Approved Regulation by stated on the Minister Order no.5 dated 12.01.2021 for the energy audit form and payment of the energy auditor. Article No. 4 of this regulation provides: Understanding and content of the Format of Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design as follows below:

- 1- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design is the document that defines the guideline to be implemented for energy auditors during the energy audit process for new buildings and buildings under design.
- 2- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design accompanies the energy performance certificate for new buildings or the preliminary energy performance certificate for buildings under design.
- 3- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design should contain a comparison between the elements considered during the design phase (their main / specific indicators on energy consumption and / or efficiency) and the issuance of the preliminary certificate and the elements of installed in the finished building according to appendix 2 attached to this instruction.

The audit report based on appendix No. 2 of this instruction of the above-mentioned Regulation shall contain at least the following elements described in detail of the buildings under design or new buildings.

1. Building envelop system

- a) Insulation
- b) Windows
- c) Air infiltrations $\Delta P = 50 \text{ Pa}$

2. Building Using Activity

3. Technical systems

- a) Heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning system
- b) Heat recovery systems
- c) Lighting systems
- d) Hot water sanitary systems

4. Energy management systems

- a) Control systems
- b) Measurement and verification systems

5. Use of alternative systems with high energy efficiency

- a) decentralized power supply systems utilizing renewable energy sources
- b) cogeneration systems, which realize the combined production of thermal energy and electrical or mechanical electricity
- c) systems with heat pumps, which change and transfer the natural flow of thermal energy, from the external environment to buildings or building units and conversely, if required
- d) Centralized heating and cooling systems, especially those that use renewable energy sources for buildings or building blocks.

Since the building under analysis is in the Design phase and will be subject to the process of obtaining a construction permit will be subject to Article 8 of Law 116/2016 For Energy Performance in Buildings,

the analysis of the possibility of using alternative systems with high energy efficiency should accompany the energy audit report for the buildings in the design phase.

2. PURPOSE OF ENERGY AUDIT

The energy audit consisted of:

- Audit of the physical construction of the building/premises.
- Audit of the heating system and domestic hot water system.
- Interviews with senior managers of the premises.
- Interrogation and discussions with the beneficiaries to obtain a typical user profile.
- Usage of relevant local climate data.

Methodology used included:

- Collection of basic information and data elaboration.
- Analyses and assessment of premises.
- Establishment of a data base for estimation of energy transmission in the premises.
- Elaboration of a consumption model for current use of energy.
- Simulation of processes for energy transmission and potential methods for energy savings.
- Establishing measures for energy savings and technical solutions.
- Technical and economic evaluation of measures for energy savings.

A detailed energy audit has been performed in line with the Terms of Reference and the Technical Proposal of the Consortium. This report is made in accordance with Albanian legislation [REF. /1/]. In addition, for a comprehensive report of the mentioned building and the systems that will be installed in it, have been used European Standards and Norms for “Energy Performance in Buildings”.

Below we will present some plans and section of the building according to the architecture project.

FIGURE 1: Plan of the apartment

FIGURE 2: The location of the apartment

FIGURE 3: Building section

FIGURE 4: Location of the object in google map

3. BUILDING USING ACTIVITY

The building under the study is located on the middle of the street: “Rruga Kongresi i Lushnjes” and street: “Rruga Ylbere Bylykbashi”, on the area “Kryqezimi 21 Dhjetori”, Tirana.

The main features and details of the building are summarized below:

- Building type: Residential building

ENERGY AUDIT REPORT

- Owner: Private
- Gross surface of the building: 71.7 m²

Summarized the condition of the buildings can be stated as follows:

- Walls are not insulated.
- Windows are single glazed with not insulated frames.
- Extensive mould occurs due to heat bridge effects.
- Roofs are not thermo-insulated, and the hydro-isolation is partly leaking.
- The Electrical System is old and in very poor condition.
- The Heating System is inefficient regarding to the new equipment's generation and standards for SEER and COP.
- The electric boiler for the domestic hot water production is old and worn out. Their performance is not good.
- Thermal comfort is very poor especially during winter.

TABLE 1: General building details

Building details		
Date of construction (year)	between 1970-1985	
Gross surface of the building	71.7 m ²	
Net surface of the building	62 m ²	
Volume of the building	200.76 m ³	(approximately)
Dimensions of the building	A = 9.96 m	
	B = 7.2 m	
	H = 2.8 m	
Number of floors	1	
Number of rooms	6	
Terrace surface	71.7 m ²	
Surface of the walls	98 m ²	
Door/ Window Surface	7.2 m ²	
Floor surface	71.7 m ²	

4. BUILDING ENVELOPE SYSTEM – *current situation*

Below will be analysed the covered structured of the building, thermal analysis and the compliance with the Albanian Legislation in force. This building is designed with supporting structure reinforced concrete pile foundations, prefabricated concrete walls, monolithic terrace.

4.1. Insulation

4.1.1 Structure of the Exterior Wall of the building

The external walls of the building are prefabricated concrete slabs with a thickness of 20 cm, installation without any insulating layers.

FIGURE 5: Exterior wall structure

TABLE 2: U-value, Structure of external surrounding walls

Description: Exterior wall						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² °C/W		0.123		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² °C/W)		0.043		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.488					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² °C/W]
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Light weight concrete	12	0.29	2.4		800	0.41
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1,800	0.02
The sum of the resistances (R)						0.672

Referring to the preliminary information for the exterior wall layers, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.488 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” for existing buildings when they undergo a significant renovation, is in value 0.40 (W/m²K), the surrounding walls of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.2 Structure of the ground floor

FIGURE 6: Ground floor structure

TABLE 3: U-value, Floor structure

Description: Ground floor						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W		0.110		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)		0.043		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.234					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to outside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Porcelain tiles	2	1	50.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Tiles adhesive	1	0.9	90.0	1	2000	0.01
Lightweight concrete screed	2	0.9	45.0		1800	0.02
Water proofing layer	0.8	0.26	32.5		1300	0.03
Reinforced concrete	20	1.91	9.6		2400	0.10
Gravel	15	2.2	14.7		2200	0.07
Soil	60	1.5	2.5		2000	0.40
The sum of the resistances						0.810

Referring to preliminary information for floor coverings, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.234 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” which is in value 0.45 (W/m²K), the floor of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.3 Ceiling structure

FIGURE 7: Ceiling structure

TABLE 4: U-value, Ceiling structure

Description: Ceiling						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W		0.110		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)		0.043		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.650					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Reinforced concrete	15	1.16	7.7	1	2000	0.13
Lightweight concrete screed	8	0.35	4.4		1000	0.23
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
Water proofing layer	1	0.26	26.0		1300	0.04
Tiles adhesive	1	0.9	90.0		1800	0.01
Porcelain tiles	2	1	50.0		2300	0.02
The sum of the resistances						0.606

Referring to preliminary information for roof coverings, it will have the composition shown above.

From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.650 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” which is iv value 0.35 (W/m²K), the covering structure of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.1 Other coefficients of the internal structures of the building

FIGURE 8: Interior wall structure

TABLE 5: U-value, Interior wall structure

Description: Interior brick wall						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W		0.123		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)		0.123		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.455					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Exterior cement plaster	2.5	0.9	36.0	0.91	1,800	0.03
Silicate brick wall	20	0.52	2.6	0.88	1,200	0.38
Gypsum plaster	2.5	0.9	36.0	0.91	1,800	0.03
The sum of the resistances (R)						0.687

5. TECHNICAL SYSTEMS

5.1.1 Heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning system

Cooling and Heating System

Efficiency demands a new rating system for heating and cooling products, which must be used by all manufacturers. These are:

- The Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) value in cooling
- The Coefficient of Performance (COP) value in heating

According to directive 2012/27/EU, products used for room air conditioning must meet minimum energy efficiency requirements.

The selected cooling and heating system for this building is a split type, using the eco-friendly refrigerant R410a. Our appliance is class B, the Energy Efficiency Ratio is EER=3.1 and the Coefficient of Performance) is COP=3.3 which are greater from the above-mentioned minimum values.

TABLE 6: Present Heating/cooling system consumption

Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Heating/cooling capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Single-split air conditioner	3.4/3.2 kW	3	1,200.00	3.60	6	21.6	7,884.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m2a)							143.35

FIGURE 9: EER / SCOP annual energy consumption and efficiency (directive 2012/27/EU)

Ventilation System

There is no mechanical or forced ventilation system installed in this apartment. Currently the air exchange in the rooms is provided accidentally by excessive air infiltration through bad quality doors and windows. Additionally, the inappropriate user behaviour (reacting to the bad building and comfort conditions) also influences the room ventilation: by leaving the doors and windows opened or closed for a long period, the following consequences can be observed:

1. High energy consumption to keep a bearable temperature (warmer or cooler) for all spaces.
2. No sufficient room ventilation can be achieved, especially in winter times.

The lack of ventilation becomes obvious in the toilet where we face the presence of mould.

5.1.2 Lighting systems

The lighting system that is used in the apartment is by fluorescent lights will high efficiency and low energy consumption luminaires with a minimum output of 58 lm / Watt efficiency.

FIGURE 10: Lumens per watt (lm/W) explained

TABLE 7: Present lighting consumption

Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	Incandescent	1	65	0.065	12	0.78	284.70
Living room	Incandescent	2	65	0.13	12	1.56	569.40
Toilet	fluorescent	2	32	0.064	12	0.768	280.32
Bedroom 1	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Bedroom 2	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Corridor	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Balcony	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Total				0.563		6.756	2,465.94
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m2a)							44.84

Minimum comfort requirements

TABLE 8: Comfort lighting levels for different typologies of residential building areas

Area typology (code)	Name of the area	Lighting ² (lux)
R&JR	Bedroom	125
	Living room	150
	Kitchen	200
	Bathroom/WC, with shower	100
	Corridor/staircase	100
² The technical requirements, the main terms for the lighting of buildings and the basic norms of lighting design are defined in the Standard SSH EN 12464-1:2011, “Light and lighting”, approved by the General Directorate of Standards, as an Albanian standard on 2012.12.20.		

5.1.3 Hot water sanitary systems

In the specific building is required low demand in hot water for use. Therefore, a local electrical water heater is installed, 2.5 kW power, 100 Liters of storage capacity, suitable to satisfy the needs of its users.

FIGURE 11: Electric boiler for hot water

TABLE 9: Present Sanitary hot water consumption

Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	2,500.00	2.5	12	30	10,950.00
Specific thermal energy (kWh/m ² a)							199.09

6. THERMAL LOSS CALCULATIONS

6.1 Thermal loss of the building

Building data

Average minimum outside temperature	0°C
Desired indoor temperature	21°C
Non heated spaces temperature	10°C
Soil temperature	10°C
Calculation method	DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003
Unit system	Watt

The following calculations show the heat transfer in the winter period.

TABLE 10: Heat losses in the winter period in actual conditions (referring to the table no.9)

Heat losses from building envelope (Wat)							
Air infiltrations	Floor	Terrace	Walls	Doors and Windows	Thermal node	Correction factor	Total heat losses (W)
4,173.8	973.3	354.9	2,691.2	1,245.0	480.3	1,190.2	11,108.7

TABLE 11: Heat losses calculation of the building

HEAT LOSSES CALCULATIONS OF THE BUILDING																			
Structures	Volume of heating spaces	ORIENTATION	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Length	Height	Surface	Surface which need to be deducted	The outer surface of the structure	Desired in door temperature (tb)	Outside temperature (ti)	Heat losses (Qt)	Heat losses in the nodes (Qn)	Heat losses (Orientation supplements)		Heat losses from the air infiltrations		Total heat losses		
													%	W	naj	W		W	
	m3		W/m ² K	m	m	m ²	m ²	m ²	°C	°C	W	W	%	W	naj	W	W		
Exterior wall	200.8	N	1.488	9.90	2.80	27.72	2.3	25.47	21	0	795.9	79.6	20	159.2	3	4173.8	1,034.7		
Exterior wall		E	1.488	7.42	2.80	20.78	2.3	18.53	21	0	578.9	57.9	10	57.9			694.7		
Exterior wall		W	1.488	7.42	2.80	20.78	2.3	18.53	21	0	578.9	57.9	15	86.8			723.6		
Exterior wall		S	1.488	4.90	2.80	13.72	2.0	11.74	21	0	366.9	36.7	0	0.0			403.5		
Interior wall		W	1.455	4.75	2.80	13.30	0.0	13.30	21	18	58.1	5.8	15	8.7			72.6		
Window		N	7.000	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	330.8	33.1	20	66.2			430.0		
Window		E	7.000	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	330.8	33.1	10	33.1			396.9		
Window		W	7.000	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	330.8	33.1	15	49.6			413.4		
Exterior door		S	2.5	0.90	2.20	1.98	0.0	1.98	21	0	104.0	10.4	0	0.0			114.3		
Floor				1.234	-	-	71.70	0.0	71.70	21	10	973.3	97.3	0			0.0		1,070.6
Terrace				1.650	-	-	71.70	0.0	71.70	21	18	354.9	35.5	0			0.0		390.4
																	Qtot	9,918.5	W
															Gv	1.36	W/m ³ °C		
SURFACE 71.7 M2						Corrections in percentage (%) for intermittent operation and load reduction											1,190.2	W	
						Continued use with reduction at night - Plant with warm air 12%													
S/V=	0.36															11,108.7	W		

6.1 Calculation of the volume heat loss coefficient G_{vt} ($W/m^3\text{°C}$)

Referring to the Building Energy Code and DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 “For the approval of norms, rules and conditions of design and construction, production and storage of heat in buildings”, calculation of the volume heat loss coefficient G_{vt} ($W/m^3\text{°C}$), is done as below:

$$G_{vt} = \frac{Q_o}{V * \Delta t} \quad (1)$$

where:

- G_{vt} - Coefficient of volume heat loss ($W/m^3\text{°C}$);
- Q_o - Heat losses from the envelope;
- V - Building volume;
- t_b - Desired indoor temperature (21°C);
- t_j - Outside temperature (0°C).

For our building the report S/V is as below:

$$\frac{S}{V} = 0.36 \quad (2)$$

where:

- S - The outer surface of the structure 71.7 m^2
- V - Volume of heating spaces 200.8 m^3

For our building we can calculate: $G_{vt} = 2.635\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$

Below table show the value of the G_{vt} (S/V report) for the building envelope based on the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003.

TABLE 12: Normative value of the volume heat loss coefficient though transmission G_{vt0}

S/V	ZONES ACCORDING TO THE GRADE DAYS					
	A		B		C	
	grade day 900 ÷ 1500		grade day 1501 ÷ 2500		grade day 2501 ÷ 3000	
≤ 0.3	0.62	0.54	0.54	0.45	0.45	0.41
≥ 0.9	1.20	1.03	1.03	0.86	0.86	0.81

Tirana region is located at climatic zone A, with 1173 Grade Days. Based on above table, part of the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 through interpolation we derive that for the report $\frac{S}{V} = 0.36$ of our building, the normative coefficient for the allow volume heat loss its $G_{vt0} = 1.58\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

From heat losses calculation shown in above table, the volume heat loss coefficient with transmission for the building analysed is $G_{vt} = 2.635\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

In our case: $G_{vt} > G_{vt0}$

As conclusion we can state that analyses building doesn't fulfils the Albanian legal requirements for the heat losses in the building.

Note: G_{v_i} is higher than $G_{v_{to}}$ which is against the condition recommended by the DCM No..38.

6.2 Calculation of the energy consumption for the heating

Needed heating energy for the building is calculated as below:

$$E_{\text{vijetore}} = \frac{Q_0 * Grd * h / dite}{\Delta t}$$

where:

- Q_0 - Heat losses from the envelope Wat;
- Grd - heating grade days (1,173);
- h/day - Number of the hours used for the heating of the building (6 hours);
- Δt - Design temperature difference (21°C).

TABLE 13: Annual energy consumption for heating before EEM

Annual energy consumption			
No.	Description	Value	Unit
1	Heat losses	11,108.7	Wat
2	Plant operating time (Continued use with reduction at night)	6	hour
3	Grade day	1,534	GRD
4	Design temperature difference	21.00	°C
5	Building surface	71.70	m ²
6	Annual thermal energy	4,868.80	kWh/a
	Annual specific consumption	67.91	kWh/m²a

As can be seen from the table above, based on the relevant data and calculations, the annual energy demand for heating of the building under analysis will be **4,868.80 kWh/a**, with a specific consumption of **67.91 kWh/ m²a**.

7. CURRENT ENERGETIC CLASSIFICATION OF THE APARTMENT

The measured energy consumption is not representative according to modern standards and comfort conditions. As there is currently no Albanian standard (fixing comfort requirements for lighting, hot sanitary water and heating) available the German ENEC standard was used to calculate the energy consumption baseline including comfort conditions.

The specific energy consumption of the building in the baseline case is **67.91 kWh/(m²a)**. Compared to the reference building defined in the German code the energy consumption of the present building is **132.5% lower**.

Compared to the Albanian Law for Energy Efficiency in buildings this value does not meets the minimum requirements of this standard.

FIGURE 12: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the reference building

FIGURE 13: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the Albanian Law

8. MEASURES FOR INCREASING THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY CLASS

Energy efficiency describes the ratio between the benefit obtained and the energy used. From an economic point of view, energy efficiency can be described as the marginal productivity of energy input, specifying how much energy is needed to produce a given level of output (heat, light, motion, comfort).

FIGURE 14: Heat losses in a building from the envelope system

Main energy saving measures

- Insulation of walls and roofs/terraces
- Installation of energy efficient windows
- Installation of an energy efficient heating system
- Installation of an energy efficient cooling system
- Use of energy-efficient electric heaters
- Use of solar water heating systems
- Installation of an efficient lighting system
- Purchase of efficient household appliances

Below are the U values for the building structures according to the Decision No. 537, date 8.7.2020

TABLE 14: Comparison of U values for building structures

Building covering elements	Value U calculated (W/m ² K)	Comments	Maximum allowable U value as defined in the regulation U max (W/m ² K)	Legal basis
Exterior walls	1.488	Should be improved	0.40	DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020
Terrace	1.650	In this case the ceiling communicates with the air-conditioned space above	0.35	
Floor	1.234	Should be improved	0.45	
Windows	7.00	Should be improved	2.20	

According to this Decision we can prove that all the U values calculated for this apartment are higher than the maximum allowable, so we must act on improvement of all building covering elements by reconfiguring the layers to improve the performance of envelope system.

8.1.1 Exterior wall insulation

Insulation of the exterior walls should be provided in case of reducing the value of the building heat loss in the heating and cooling conditions.

FIGURE 15: External wall insulation layers

TABLE 15: U-value, Exterior wall structure – proposed

Description: Exterior wall - Proposed						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² °C/W		0.123		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² °C/W)		0.043		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	0.386					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² °C/W]
EIFS plaster	2.5	0.79	31.6		1,600	0.03
Insulation board + adhesive + reinforcing mesh	8	0.039	0.5		20	2.05
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Light weight concrete	12	0.29	2.4		800	0.41
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1,800	0.02
The sum of the resistances (R)						2.588

FIGURE 16: Comparison of heat transmission coefficients for different thicknesses

8.1.1 Ground floor insulation

TABLE 16: U-value, Floor structure – proposed

Description: Ground floor - Proposed						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m²·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m²C/W	0.110			
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m²·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m²C/W)	0.043			
Coefficient U [W/(m²·K)]:	0.295					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to outside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m²·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m³]	[m²C/W]
Laminate floor	0.8	0.2	25.0		900	0.04
Lightweight concrete screed	3	0.9	30.0		1800	0.03
Insulation board XPS	10	0.039	0.4			2.56
Water proofing layer	0.8	0.26	32.5		1300	0.03
Reinforced concrete	20	1.91	9.6		2400	0.10
Gravel	15	2.2	14.7		2200	0.07
Soil	60	1.5	2.5		2000	0.40
The sum of the resistances						3.394

8.1.2 Replacing Windows, Reducing the K coefficient

The windows in the apartment consist of none insulated aluminium frames with single glazed sliding panels. The thermal quality therefore is very poor. In conclusion, the improvement/replacement of the

windows will be done for all apartment, in case to reduce the monthly bill (these windows with such elements reduce the infiltration of air and the loss of solar heat, reducing the amount of energy for heating and cooling the building).

Another small improvement can be the use of warm plastic spacers joining the glass pane instead of the typical aluminium option. The size of the gap between the glass is important too. Best windows offer 18mm space in the triple-glazed version and 24mm in double-glazed windows.

FIGURE 17: Single pane, double pane and triple pane glass window

TABLE 19

Overall U-factors (heat transfer coefficients) for various windows and skylights in $W/m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$ (from ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamentals, Chap. 27, Table 5)

Type	Glass section (glazing) only		Aluminum frame (without thermal break)			Wood or vinyl frame						
	Center-of-glass	Edge-of-glass	Fixed	Double door	Sloped skylight	Fixed	Double door	Sloped skylight				
Frame width →	(Not applicable)		32 mm (1 1/4 in)	53 mm (2 in)	19 mm (3/4 in)	41 mm (1 1/4 in)	88 mm (3 7/16 in)	23 mm (1 in)				
Spacer type →	—	Metal Insul.	All	All	All	Metal Insul.	Metal Insul.	Metal Insul.	Metal Insul.			
Glazing Type												
Single Glazing												
3 mm (1/8 in) glass	6.30	6.30	—	6.63	7.16	9.88	5.93	—	5.57	—	7.57	—
6.4 mm (1/4 in) acrylic	5.28	5.28	—	5.69	6.27	8.86	5.02	—	4.77	—	6.57	—
3 mm (1/8 in) acrylic	5.79	5.79	—	6.16	6.71	9.94	5.48	—	5.17	—	7.63	—
Double Glazing (no coating)												
6.4 mm air space	3.24	3.71	3.34	3.90	4.55	6.70	3.26	3.16	3.20	3.09	4.37	4.22
12.7 mm air space	2.78	3.40	2.91	3.51	4.18	6.65	2.88	2.76	2.86	2.74	4.32	4.17
6.4 mm argon space	2.95	3.52	3.07	3.66	4.32	6.47	3.03	2.91	2.98	2.87	4.14	3.97
12.7 mm argon space	2.61	3.28	2.76	3.36	4.04	6.47	2.74	2.61	2.73	2.60	4.14	3.97
Double Glazing [$\epsilon = 0.1$, coating on one of the surfaces of air space (surface 2 or 3, counting from the outside toward inside)]												
6.4 mm air space	2.44	3.16	2.60	3.21	3.89	6.04	2.59	2.46	2.60	2.47	3.73	3.53
12.7 mm air space	1.82	2.71	2.06	2.67	3.37	6.04	2.06	1.92	2.13	1.99	3.73	3.53
6.4 mm argon space	1.99	2.83	2.21	2.82	3.52	5.62	2.21	2.07	2.26	2.12	3.32	3.09
12.7 mm argon space	1.53	2.49	1.83	2.42	3.14	5.71	1.82	1.67	1.91	1.78	3.41	3.19
Triple Glazing (no coating)												
6.4 mm air space	2.16	2.96	2.35	2.97	3.66	5.81	2.34	2.18	2.36	2.21	3.48	3.24
12.7 mm air space	1.76	2.67	2.02	2.62	3.33	5.67	2.01	1.84	2.07	1.91	3.34	3.09
6.4 mm argon space	1.93	2.79	2.16	2.77	3.47	5.57	2.15	1.99	2.19	2.04	3.25	3.00
12.7 mm argon space	1.65	2.58	1.92	2.52	3.23	5.53	1.91	1.74	1.98	1.82	3.20	2.95
Triple Glazing [$\epsilon = 0.1$, coating on one of the surfaces of air spaces (surfaces 3 and 5, counting from the outside toward inside)]												
6.4 mm air space	1.53	2.49	1.83	2.42	3.14	5.24	1.81	1.64	1.89	1.73	2.92	2.66
12.7 mm air space	0.97	2.05	1.38	1.92	2.66	5.10	1.33	1.15	1.46	1.30	2.78	2.52
6.4 mm argon space	1.19	2.23	1.56	2.12	2.85	4.90	1.52	1.35	1.64	1.47	2.59	2.33
12.7 mm argon space	0.80	1.92	1.25	1.77	2.51	4.86	1.18	1.01	1.33	1.17	2.55	2.28

TABLE 17: Overall U-value for various windows (according to ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamentals)

The type of window that we have selected for the replacement of the old ones is the one significant in the red square.

8.1.1 Replacing the lighting system

The following measures are recommended:

- Replacing the incandescent and fluorescent lamps (CFL) currently installed with LED lamps ensuring also the actual required illumination value.

FIGURE 18: Energy saving vs Energy consumption on lighting systems

8.1.1 Increasing the efficiency of the heating/cooling system

The new system selected for heating and cooling this apartment must belong to class A of energy efficiency, with the Energy Efficiency Ratio EER > 3.2 and the Coefficient of Performance COP > 3.6.

9. THERMAL LOSS CALCULATIONS

TABLE 18: Heat losses in the winter period after AEE (referring to the table no.19)

Heat losses from building envelope after AEE (Wat)							
Air infiltrations	Floor	Terrace	Walls	Doors and Windows	Thermal node	Correction factor	Total heat losses (W)
4,173.8	232.7	354.9	812.8	188.8	147.7	709.3	6,619.9

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TABLE 19: Heat losses calculation of the building after EEM

HEAT LOSSES CALCULATIONS OF THE BUILDING AFTER EEM																		
Structures	Volume of heating spaces	ORIENTATION	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Length	Height	Surface	Surface which need to be deduced	The outer surface of the structure	Desired indoor temperature (tb)	Outside temperature (tj)	Heat losses (Qt)	Heat losses in the nodes (Qn)	Heat losses (Orientation supplements)		Heat losses from the air infiltrations		Total heat losses	
	m3		W/m²·K	m	m	m²	m²	m²	°C	°C	W	W	%	W	naj	W	W	
Exterior wall	200.8	N	0.386	9.90	2.80	27.72	2.3	25.47	21	0	206.5	20.6	20	41.3	3	4173.8	268.4	
Exterior wall		E	0.386	7.42	2.80	20.78	2.3	18.53	21	0	150.2	15.0	10	15.0			180.2	
Exterior wall		W	0.386	7.42	2.80	20.78	2.3	18.53	21	0	150.2	15.0	15	22.5			187.7	
Exterior wall		S	0.386	4.90	2.80	13.72	2.0	11.74	21	0	95.2	9.5	0	0.0			104.7	
Interior wall		W	1.455	4.75	2.80	13.30	0.0	13.30	21	18	58.1	5.8	15	8.7			72.6	
Window		N	1.150	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	54.3	5.4	20	10.9			70.6	
Window		E	1.150	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	54.3	5.4	10	5.4			65.2	
Window		W	1.150	1.50	1.50	2.25	0.0	2.25	21	0	54.3	5.4	15	8.2			67.9	
Exterior door		S	1.6	0.90	2.20	1.98	0.0	1.98	21	0	66.5	6.7	0	0.0			73.2	
Floor				0.295	-	-	71.70	0.0	71.70	21	10	232.7	23.3	0			0.0	255.9
Ceiling				1.650	-	-	71.70	0.0	71.70	21	18	354.9	35.5	0			0.0	390.4
																	Qtot	5,910.7
															Gv	0.41	W/m³°C	
SURFACE 71.7 M2						Corrections in percentage (%) for intermittent operation and load reduction										709.3	W	
						Continued use with reduction at night - Plant with warm air 12%												
S/V=	0.36															6,619.9	W	

Based on the previous information's, part of the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 through interpolation we derive that for the report $\frac{S}{V} = 0.36$ of our building is the same as before, the normative coefficient for the allow volume heat loss its $G_{vt0} = 1.58 \text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

From heat losses calculation shown in above table, the new volume heat loss coefficient with transmission for the building analysed is $G_{vt} = 1.57 \text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

In our case: $G_{vt} \leq G_{vt0}$

As conclusion we can state that analyses building after EEM fulfils the Albanian legal requirements for the heat losses in the building.

Note: G_{vt} is lower than G_{vt0} which is against the condition recommended by the DCM No..38.

10. ENERGETIC CLASSIFICATION OF THE APARTMENT AFTER EEM

TABLE 20: Annual energy consumption for heating before EEM

Annual energy consumption			
No.	Description	Value	Unit
1	Heat losses	6,619.9	Wat
2	Plant operating time (Continued use with reduction at night)	6	hour
3	Grade day	1,534	GRD
4	Design temperature difference	21.00	°C
5	Building surface	71.70	m ²
6	Annual thermal energy	2,901.42	kWh/a
	Annual specific consumption	40.47	kWh/m²a

FIGURE 19: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the new building conditions

FIGURE 20: Classification of Energy Class regarding to the Albanian Law

11. COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

The estimated costs of the structural and comfort measures are based on official cost tables provided by the Ministry of Transport & Infrastructure¹ and on Albanian market prices.

The costs are estimated for the structural measures which are fundamental and should be realized before or in combination with further energy efficiency measures.

TABLE 21: Electrical consumption and costs before EEM

¹ REF. [28] Technical Manuals MD 2012, Official Bulletin 83- 2012, <http://www.mppt.gov.al/>

Electrical consumption before EEM							
Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	Incandescent	1	65	0.065	12	0.78	284.70
Living room	Incandescent	2	65	0.13	12	1.56	569.40
Toilet	fluorescent	2	32	0.064	12	0.768	280.32
Bedroom 1	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Bedroom 2	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Corridor	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Balcony	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Total				0.563		6.756	2,465.94
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							44.84
Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Heating/cooling capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Single-split air conditioner	3.4/3.2 kW	3	1,200.00	3.60	6	21.6	7,884.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							143.35
Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	2,500.00	2.5	12	30	10,950.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							199.09
Total Electrical Annual consumption (kWh/a)							21,299.94
The price of electricity (euro/kWh)							0.14
Total price of Electrical Annual consumption before EEM (euro/kWh/a)							2,981.99

TABLE 22: Electrical consumption and costs after EEM

Electrical consumption after EEM							
Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	LED	1	20	0.02	12	0.24	87.60
Living room	LED	1	30	0.03	12	0.36	131.40
Toilet	LED	1	10	0.01	12	0.12	43.80
Bedroom 1	LED	1	15	0.015	12	0.18	65.70
Bedroom 2	LED	1	15	0.015	12	0.18	65.70
Corridor	LED	1	10	0.01	12	0.12	43.80
Balcony	LED	1	5	0.005	12	0.06	21.90
Total				0.105		1.26	459.90
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m2a)							8.36
Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Annual consumption (kWh/a)			COP		Annual consumption (kWh/a)	
Single-split air conditioner	5,802.8			3.8		1,527.06	
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m2a)							27.76
Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	1,200.00	1.2	12	14.4	5,256.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m2a)							95.56
ELECTRICAL COST							
Total Electrical Annual consumption (kWh/a)							7,242.96
The price of electricity (euro/kWh)							0.14
Total price of Electrical Annual consumption after EEM (euro)							1,014.01

TABLE 23: Total investment value for EEM

Building Envelope Measures	Unit	Qty	Unit price [€]	Investment Cost [€]
Preparation for the EE Measures (demolition, transportation, cleaning up)	m2	71.70	10 €	717.00 €
External wall envelope (thermal insulation EPS thickness 8 cm)	m2	69.30	25.00 €	1,732.50 €
Windows Renewal ≤ 1.4 W/m2K	m2	9.00	140.00 €	1,260.00 €
Thermo-insulation of the Floor (XPS thickness 10 cm)	m3	7.17	100.00 €	717.00 €

Lightweight concrete screed for floor (3 cm layer)	m3	2.15	110.00 €	236.61 €
Laminate floor 0.8 cm	m2	71.70	15.00 €	1,075.50 €
TOTAL COSTS 1 (€)				5,738.61 €
Other EE Measures	Unit	Qty	Unit price [€]	Investment Cost [€]
Heating/cooling Air Condition system	pcs	3.00	650 €	1,950 €
DHW: 50% Solar Thermal Panels + 50% Air Heat Pumps	pcs	-	-	1,125.00 €
Photovoltaic panels	pcs	-	-	1,323.00 €
Lighting (CFL + LED)	pcs	7.00	80 €	560 €
TOTAL COSTS 2 (€)				4,958.00 €
TOTAL COSTS without Solar and photovoltaic panels [1+2] (€)				8,248.61 €
TOTAL COSTS with Solar and photovoltaic panels [1+2] (€)				10,696.61 €

TABLE 24: Savings and investment repayment time

Total cost of Electrical Annual consumption before EEM (euro)	Total cost of Electrical Annual consumption after EEM (euro)	Annual savings (euro)	Total Investment value (euro)	Payback period (years)
2,981.99 €	1,014.01 €	1,967.98 €	8,248.61 €	4.2

12. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Analysis done for the baseline show that the apartment taken in analyse has an energy consumption of **67.91 kWh/m²a**, classifying in **ENERGY CLASSES C**, which according to the **Albanian law (*Law no. 116 date 10.11.2016 for Energy Efficiency in Buildings*)**.

In based of such analysis its recommended to be done some interventions which will bring the apartment **40.47 kWh/m²a**, in **ENERGY CLASSES B**, fulfilling the requirements of Albanian law.

Needed interventions:

- Insulation for the entire building envelope
- Replacing the lighting system from CFL and Incandescent lights to LED
- Replacing the electric boiler from standard on/off to smart boilers that saves up to 20% energy
- Replacement of the old mono-split heating/cooling non inverter to new equipment's with higher performance and inverter

Further recommendations for increasing the **ENERGY CLASSES** from **B** to **A**:

- Replacing the electric boilers with solar panels for generating hot sanitary water
- Installation of photovoltaic panels to save electrical energy and use of its energy for heating/cooling system.

ENERGY AUDIT REPORT

ENERGY EFFICIENCY REHABILITATION OF

OBJECT: *Building no.9, 3rd floor, Apartment no. 4*

PROJECT: *GreenFORCE - Foster Research Excellence for Green
Transition in the Western Balkans*

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ABBREVIATIONS

AKBN	National Agency of Natural Resources
AKPT	National Agency for Territorial Planning
AL	Albania
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineers
BMS	Building Management System
DCM	Decision Council Ministerial
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
ECM	Efficiency Component Measures
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measures
EN	European Norms
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPS	Expanded Polystyrene
ETICS	External thermal insulation compound system
EU	European Union
GFA	Gross Floor Area
GoA	Government of Albania
HDD	Heating degree days
IP	Inception Phase of Project
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol 1000-1:2010
MEI	Ministry of Energy and Industry
METDE	Ministry of Economic Development, Trade and Enterprise
MoM	Meeting of Minutes
MoT	Municipality of Tirana
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
P	The Project
RE	Renewable Energy
SYM	SymbioticA, Local Project Coordination Office of Consultant
ToR	Terms of Reference (from "Instructions to tenderers" by KfW)
TP	Technical Proposal
U	Coefficient of heat transmission
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
U _w	Coefficient of heat transmission of a window (including frame and glazing)
WB	Western Balkans

ENERGY AUDIT REPORT

XPS	Extruded Polystyrene
λ	Thermal conductivity
€	Euro – Euro currency rate to AL Leke is taken 1€=100 Leke

TABLE OF UNITS

Description	Symbol	Measuring unit
Heat transfer coefficient	U	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Glass surface	Ag	[m ²]
Window frame surface	Af	[m ²]
Length of glass surface	Lg	[m]
Heat transfer from glass element	Kg	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Heat transfer from frame	Kf	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Linear heat transmission	Kl	[W/(m·K)]
Total heat transfer of frame	Kw	[W/(m ² ·K)]
Volume	Vol.	[m ³]
Wet thermometer temperature	Tdb	[°C]
Relative humidity	R.H.	[%]
Heat losses	H.L.	[W]
Feed rate	V	[m ³ /h]
Length	L	[m]
Net Surface	S	[m ²]
Increased security	Inc.	[%]
Temperature difference	ΔT	[K]

LAWS & STANDARDS

- REF. /1/ Law no. 124/2015 for energy efficiency
- REF. /2/ Law no. 116/2016 for the energy performance of buildings
- REF. /3/ Regulation no.5 dated 12.01.2021 for the energy audit form and
- REF. /4/ payment of the energy auditor.
- REF. /5/ DCM No. 1094 dated 24.12.2020 For the Approval of the National Methodology for calculating the performance of Energy in Buildings.
- REF. /6/ Decision no. 537, dated 8.7.2020 on the approval of the
- REF. /7/ minimum energy performance requirements of
- REF. /8/ buildings and building elements
- REF. /9/ Decision no. 480, dated 31.7.2018 for the approval of the national energy strategy for the period 2018–2030
- REF. /10/ Decision no. 958, dated 2.12.2020 for the approval of the procedures and
- REF. /11/ Conditions for the certification of the energy performance of buildings and the model, the content of the conditions for the registration of the "energy performance certificate of buildings"
- REF. /12/ Decision no.256, dated 27.3.2020 on the approval of the methodology for the calculation of optimal cost levels for the minimum energy performance requirements of buildings, units and building elements
- REF. /13/ Law NO.9379, dated 28.4.2005 "For Energy Efficiency"
- REF. /14/ Law no. 8937, dated 12.09.2002, On heat storage in buildings "
- REF. /15/ EN-ISO 10077 (2006) - Thermal transmission of windows, doors - Calculation of heat transfer
- REF. /16/ DIN V 18599-2: 2007-02 - Energy Efficiency in Buildings
- REF. /17/ EnEV 2014 - Energy Saving Rules
- REF. /18/ DCM No. 38, dated 16.01.2003, "On the approval of norms, rules and conditions of design and construction, production and storage of heat in buildings".
- REF. /19/ UNI EN 806 - "Specifications for indoor installations for water systems for human use"
- REF. /20/ EN ISO 13790 2008 "Thermal performance of buildings - Calculations for energy use for heating and cooling of premises";
- REF. /21/ EN- ISO 13789 (2007) "Thermal performance of buildings-Coefficients of heat transfer with transmission and ventilation, Calculation method";
- REF. /22/ EN-ISO 13370 (2007) - Thermal performance of the building - Heat transfer from the ground-Calculation method
- REF. /23/ EN-ISO 10456 (2007) - Building products and materials - Tables of values and procedures for determining the thermal values
- REF. /24/ EN-ISO 9251– Thermal Insulation - Conditions of heat transfer and characteristics of materials
- REF. /25/ EN ISO 7345- Thermal insulation - Physical quantities and definitions
- REF. /26/ EN-ISO 6946 (2007) - Building components and building elements - Thermal resistance and thermal transmission - Calculation method
- REF. /27/ DCM No. 853, dated 14.11.2007, "Use of compact fluorescent lamps
- REF. /28/ Directive 2012/27 / EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency
- REF. /29/ EN 15603 (2008) - Energy Performance of Buildings - General Energy Use and Definition of Energy Evaluation
- REF. /30/ EN 15459: 2006 - Energy efficiency in buildings - Standard economic evaluation procedures for energy systems in buildings

- REF. /31/ UNI 10339: 1995 - Air Conditioning Systems for Thermal Comfort in Buildings. General, classification and requirements. Offer, purpose and specifications of the supply
- REF. /32/ EN 15378 (2007) - Heating system of buildings – Inspection of boilers and heating systems
- REF. /33/ EN 15316 (2007) - Heating systems in buildings - Method of calculation of energy requirements of systems and efficiency of systems
- REF. /34/ EN 15239 (2007) - Ventilation of buildings - Energy performance of buildings - Guidelines for inspection of ventilation systems
- REF. /35/ EN 15193 (2007) - Energy performance of buildings - Energy requirements for lighting
- REF. /36/ REF. / 36 / DIN V 18599-10: 2007-02 - Energy efficiency in buildings - Calculation of energy needs, energy supplied, and primary energy for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting. - Part 10: Boundary conditions of use, climatic data
- REF. /37/ Technical Manuals DCM 27.06.2012. Official Journal 83-2012

1. INTRODUCTION

This report has been drafted in accordance with the Approved Regulation by stated on the Minister Order no.5 dated 12.01.2021 for the energy audit form and payment of the energy auditor. Article No. 4 of this regulation provides: Understanding and content of the Format of Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design as follows below:

- 1- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design is the document that defines the guideline to be implemented for energy auditors during the energy audit process for new buildings and buildings under design.
- 2- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design accompanies the energy performance certificate for new buildings or the preliminary energy performance certificate for buildings under design.
- 3- Energy Audit Report for new buildings and buildings under design should contain a comparison between the elements considered during the design phase (their main / specific indicators on energy consumption and / or efficiency) and the issuance of the preliminary certificate and the elements of installed in the finished building according to appendix 2 attached to this instruction.

The audit report based on appendix No. 2 of this instruction of the above-mentioned Regulation shall contain at least the following elements described in detail of the buildings under design or new buildings.

1. Building envelop system

- a) Insulation
- b) Windows
- c) Air infiltrations $\Delta P = 50 \text{ Pa}$

2. Building Using Activity

3. Technical systems

- a) Heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning system
- b) Heat recovery systems
- c) Lighting systems
- d) Hot water sanitary systems

4. Energy management systems

- a) Control systems
- b) Measurement and verification systems

5. Use of alternative systems with high energy efficiency

- a) decentralized power supply systems utilizing renewable energy sources
- b) cogeneration systems, which realize the combined production of thermal energy and electrical or mechanical electricity
- c) systems with heat pumps, which change and transfer the natural flow of thermal energy, from the external environment to buildings or building units and conversely, if required
- d) Centralized heating and cooling systems, especially those that use renewable energy sources for buildings or building blocks.

Since the building under analysis is in the Design phase and will be subject to the process of obtaining a construction permit will be subject to Article 8 of Law 116/2016 For Energy Performance in Buildings,

the analysis of the possibility of using alternative systems with high energy efficiency should accompany the energy audit report for the buildings in the design phase.

2. PURPOSE OF ENERGY AUDIT

The energy audit consisted of:

- Audit of the physical construction of the building/premises.
- Audit of the heating system and domestic hot water system.
- Interviews with senior managers of the premises.
- Interrogation and discussions with the beneficiaries to obtain a typical user profile.
- Usage of relevant local climate data.

Methodology used included:

- Collection of basic information and data elaboration.
- Analyses and assessment of premises.
- Establishment of a data base for estimation of energy transmission in the premises.
- Elaboration of a consumption model for current use of energy.
- Simulation of processes for energy transmission and potential methods for energy savings.
- Establishing measures for energy savings and technical solutions.
- Technical and economic evaluation of measures for energy savings.

A detailed energy audit has been performed in line with the Terms of Reference and the Technical Proposal of the Consortium. This report is made in accordance with Albanian legislation [REF. /1/]. In addition, for a comprehensive report of the mentioned building and the systems that will be installed in it, have been used European Standards and Norms for “Energy Performance in Buildings”.

Below we will present some plans and section of the building according to the architecture project.

FIGURE 1: Plan of the apartment

FIGURE 2: The location of the apartment

FIGURE 3: Building section

FIGURE 4: Real photo of the object

FIGURE 5: Location of the object in google map

3. BUILDING USING ACTIVITY

The building under the study is located on the middle of the street: “Rruga Kongresi i Lushnjes” and street: “Rruga Ylberë Bylykbashi”, on the area “Kryqezimi 21 Dhjetori”, Tirana.

The main features and details of the building are summarized below:

- Building type: Residential building
- Owner: Private
- Gross surface of the building: 90 m²

Summarized the condition of the buildings can be stated as follows:

- Walls are not insulated.
- Windows are single glazed with not insulated frames.
- Extensive mould occurs due to heat bridge effects.
- Roofs are not thermo-insulated, and the hydro-isolation is partly leaking.
- The Electrical System is old and in very poor condition.
- The Heating System is inefficient regarding to the new equipment’s generation and standards for SEER and COP.
- The electric boiler for the domestic hot water production is old and worn out. Their performance is not good.
- Thermal comfort is very poor especially during winter.

TABLE 1: General building details

Building details		
Date of construction (year)	between 1970-1985	
Gross surface of the building	90 m ²	
Net surface of the building	82 m ²	
Volume of the building	252 m ³	(approximately)
Dimensions of the building	A = 10.9 m	
	B = 9.9 m	
	H = 2.8 m	
Number of floors	1	
Number of rooms	7	
Terrace surface	90 m ²	
Surface of the walls	98 m ²	
Door/ Window Surface	15.2 m ²	
Floor surface	90 m ²	

4. BUILDING ENVELOPE SYSTEM – *current situation*

Below will be analysed the covered structured of the building, thermal analysis and the compliance with the Albanian Legislation in force. This building is designed with supporting structure reinforced concrete pile foundations, prefabricated concrete walls, monolithic terrace.

4.1. Insulation

4.1.1 Structure of the Exterior Wall of the building

The external walls of the building are prefabricated concrete slabs with a thickness of 20 cm, installation without any insulating layers.

FIGURE 6: Exterior wall structure

TABLE 2: U-value, Structure of external surrounding walls

Description: Exterior wall						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W			0.123	
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)			0.043	
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.488					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Light weight concrete	12	0.29	2.4		800	0.41
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1,800	0.02
The sum of the resistances (R)						0.672

Referring to the preliminary information for the exterior wall layers, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.488 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” for existing buildings when they undergo a significant renovation, is in value 0.40 (W/m²K), the surrounding walls of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.2 Structure of the floor

FIGURE 7: Floor structure

TABLE 3: U-value, Floor structure

Description: Floor						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W		0.110		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)		0.043		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.650					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Reinforced concrete	15	1.16	7.7	1	2000	0.13
Lightweight concrete screed	8	0.35	4.4		1000	0.23
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
Water proofing layer	1	0.26	26.0		1300	0.04
Tiles adhesive	1	0.9	90.0		1800	0.01
Porcelain tiles	2	1	50.0		2300	0.02
The sum of the resistances						0.606

Referring to preliminary information for floor coverings, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.650 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” which is in value 0.45 (W/m²K), the floor of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.3 Ceiling structure

FIGURE 8: Ceiling structure

TABLE 4: U-value, Ceiling structure

Description: Ceiling						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	9.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W	0.110			
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)	0.043			
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.650					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of Terrace structures from inside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1800	0.02
Reinforced concrete	15	1.16	7.7	1	2000	0.13
Lightweight concrete screed	8	0.35	4.4		1000	0.23
Cement mortar	3	10.4	346.7		2000	0.00
Water proofing layer	1	0.26	26.0		1300	0.04
Tiles adhesive	1	0.9	90.0		1800	0.01
Porcelain tiles	2	1	50.0		2300	0.02
The sum of the resistances						0.606

Referring to preliminary information for roof coverings, it will have the composition shown above. From the calculations of the heat transfer coefficient, it results that it will be in the value of 1.650 (W/m²K).

Compared to the limit value according to the DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020 “For the Approval of the Minimum Energy Performance Requirements of Buildings and Building Elements” which is iv value 0.35 (W/m²K), the covering structure of the building under study does not meet this criterion.

4.1.1 Other coefficients of the internal structures of the building

FIGURE 9: Interior wall structure

TABLE 5: U-value, Interior wall structure

Description: Interior brick wall						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ² C/W		0.123		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ² C/W)		0.123		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	1.455					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ² C/W]
Exterior cement plaster	2.5	0.9	36.0	0.91	1,800	0.03
Silicate brick wall	20	0.52	2.6	0.88	1,200	0.38
Gypsum plaster	2.5	0.9	36.0	0.91	1,800	0.03
The sum of the resistances (R)						0.687

5. TECHNICAL SYSTEMS

5.1.1 Heating, cooling, ventilation, and air conditioning system

Cooling and Heating System

Efficiency demands a new rating system for heating and cooling products, which must be used by all manufacturers. These are:

- The Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) value in cooling
- The Coefficient of Performance (COP) value in heating

According to directive 2012/27/EU, products used for room air conditioning must meet minimum energy efficiency requirements.

The selected cooling and heating system for this building is a split type, using the eco-friendly refrigerant R410a. Our appliance is class B, the Energy Efficiency Ratio is EER=3.1 and the Coefficient of Performance) is COP=3.3 which are greater from the above-mentioned minimum values.

TABLE 6: Present Heating/cooling system consumption

Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Heating/cooling capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Single-split air conditioner	3.4/3.2 kW	4	1,200.00	4.80	6	28.8	10,512.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m ² a)							191.13

FIGURE 10: EER / SCOP annual energy consumption and efficiency (directive 2012/27/EU)

Ventilation System

There is no mechanical or forced ventilation system installed in this apartment. Currently the air exchange in the rooms is provided accidentally by excessive air infiltration through bad quality doors and windows. Additionally, the inappropriate user behaviour (reacting to the bad building and comfort conditions) also influences the room ventilation: by leaving the doors and windows opened or closed for a long period, the following consequences can be observed:

1. High energy consumption to keep a bearable temperature (warmer or cooler) for all spaces.
2. No sufficient room ventilation can be achieved, especially in winter times.

The lack of ventilation becomes obvious in the toilet where we face the presence of mould.

5.1.2 Lighting systems

The lighting system that is used in the apartment is by fluorescent lights will high efficiency and low energy consumption luminaires with a minimum output of 58 lm / Watt efficiency.

FIGURE 11: Lumens per watt (lm/W) explained

TABLE 7: Present lighting consumption

Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	Incandescent	1	65	0.065	12	0.78	284.70
Living room	Incandescent	2	65	0.13	12	1.56	569.40
Toilet	fluorescent	2	32	0.064	12	0.768	280.32
Bedroom 1	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Bedroom 2	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Bedroom 3	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Corridor	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Balcony	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Total				0.683		8.196	2,991.54
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m2a)							54.39

Minimum comfort requirements

TABLE 8: Comfort lighting levels for different typologies of residential building areas

Area typology (code)	Name of the area	Lighting ² (lux)
R&JR	Bedroom	125
	Living room	150
	Kitchen	200
	Bathroom/WC, with shower	100
	Corridor/staircase	100
² The technical requirements, the main terms for the lighting of buildings and the basic norms of lighting design are defined in the Standard SSH EN 12464-1:2011, "Light and lighting", approved by the General Directorate of Standards, as an Albanian standard on 2012.12.20.		

5.1.3 Hot water sanitary systems

In the specific building is required low demand in hot water for use. Therefore, a local electrical water heater is installed, 2.5 kW power, 100 Litres of storage capacity, suitable to satisfy the needs of its users.

FIGURE 12: Electric boiler for hot water

TABLE 9: Present Sanitary hot water consumption

Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	2,500.00	2.5	12	30	10,950.00
Specific thermal energy (kWh/m ² a)							199.09

6. THERMAL LOSS CALCULATIONS

6.1 Thermal loss of the building

Building data

Average minimum outside temperature	0°C
Desired indoor temperature	21°C
Non heated spaces temperature	10°C
Soil temperature	10°C
Calculation method	DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003
Unit system	Watt

The following calculations show the heat transfer in the winter period.

TABLE 10: Heat losses in the winter period in actual conditions (referring to the table no.9)

Heat losses from building envelope (Wat)							
Air infiltrations	Floor	Terrace	Walls	Doors and Windows	Thermal node	Correction factor	Total heat losses (W)
5,239.1	445.5	445.5	2,491.3	1,658.5	450.0	1,287.6	12,017.4

TABLE 11: Heat losses calculation of the building

HEAT LOSSES CALCULATIONS OF THE BUILDING																		
Structures	Volume of heating spaces	ORIENTATION	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Length	Height	Surface	Surface which need to be deducted	The outer surface of the structure	Desired in door temperature (tb)	Outside temperature (ti)	Heat losses (Qt)	Heat losses in the nodes (Qt)	Heat losses (Orientation supplements)		Heat losses from the air infiltrations		Total heat losses	
	m3		W/m ² ·K	m	m	m ²	m ²	m ²	°C	°C	W	W	%	W	naj	W	W	
Exterior wall	252.0	N	1.488	10.94	2.80	30.63	4.5	26.13	21	0	816.6	81.7	20	163.3	3	5239.1	1,061.5	
Exterior wall		S	1.488	10.94	2.80	30.63	4.5	26.13	21	0	816.6	81.7	10	81.7			979.9	
Exterior wall		W	1.488	4.90	2.80	13.72	2.0	11.74	21	0	366.9	36.7	15	55.0			458.6	
Interior wall		W	1.455	5.00	2.80	14.00	0.0	14.00	21	18	61.1	6.1	15	9.2			76.4	
Interior wall		E	1.455	9.90	2.80	27.72	0.0	27.72	21	18	121.0	12.1	0	0.0			133.1	
Window		N	7.000	3.00	1.50	4.50	0.0	4.50	21	0	661.5	66.2	20	132.3			860.0	
Window		S	7.000	3.00	1.50	4.50	0.0	4.50	21	0	661.5	66.2	15	99.2			826.9	
Exterior door		W	2.5	0.90	2.20	1.98	0.0	1.98	21	0	104.0	10.4	0	0.0			114.3	
Floor				1.650	-	-	90.00	0.0	90.00	21	18	445.5	44.6	0			0.0	490.1
Terrace				1.650	-	-	90.00	0.0	90.00	21	18	445.5	44.6	0			0.0	490.1
															Qtot	10,729.8	W	
															Gv	1.04	W/m ³ °C	
SURFACE 90 M2						Corrections in persentage (%) for intermittent operation and load reduction											1,287.6	W
						Continued use with reduction at night - Plant with warm air 12%												
S/V=	0.36																12,017.4	W

6.1 Calculation of the volume heat loss coefficient G_{vt} ($W/m^3\text{°C}$)

Referring to the Building Energy Code and DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 “For the approval of norms, rules and conditions of design and construction, production and storage of heat in buildings”, calculation of the volume heat loss coefficient G_{vt} ($W/m^3\text{°C}$), is done as below:

$$G_{vt} = \frac{Q_o}{V * \Delta t} \quad (1)$$

where:

- G_{vt} - Coefficient of volume heat loss ($W/m^3\text{°C}$);
- Q_o - Heat losses from the envelope;
- V - Building volume;
- t_b - Desired indoor temperature (21°C);
- t_j - Outside temperature (0°C).

For our building the report S/V is as below:

$$\frac{S}{V} = 0.36 \quad (2)$$

where:

- S - The outer surface of the structure 90 m^2
- V - Volume of heating spaces 252.0 m^3

For our building we can calculate: $G_{vt} = 2.271\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$

Below table show the value of the G_{vt} (S/V report) for the building envelope based on the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003.

TABLE 12: Normative value of the volume heat loss coefficient though transmission G_{vt0}

S/V	ZONES ACCORDING TO THE GRADE DAYS					
	A		B		C	
	grade day 900 ÷ 1500		grade day 1501 ÷ 2500		grade day 2501 ÷ 3000	
≤ 0.3	0.62	0.54	0.54	0.45	0.45	0.41
≥ 0.9	1.20	1.03	1.03	0.86	0.86	0.81

Tirana region is located at climatic zone A, with 1173 Grade Days. Based on above table, part of the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 through interpolation we derive that for the report $\frac{S}{V} = 0.36$ of our building, the normative coefficient for the allow volume heat loss its $G_{vt0} = 1.58\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

From heat losses calculation shown in above table, the volume heat loss coefficient with transmission for the building analysed is $G_{vt} = 2.271\text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

In our case: $G_{vt} > G_{vt0}$

As conclusion we can state that analyses building doesn't fulfils the Albanian legal requirements for the heat losses in the building.

Note: G_{v_i} is higher than $G_{v_{to}}$ which is against the condition recommended by the DCM No..38.

6.2 Calculation of the energy consumption for the heating

Needed heating energy for the building is calculated as below:

$$E_{\text{vijetore}} = \frac{Q_0 * Grd * h / dite}{\Delta t}$$

where:

- Q_0 - Heat losses from the envelope Wat;
- Grd - heating grade days (1,173);
- h/day - Number of the hours used for the heating of the building (6 hours);
- Δt - Design temperature difference (21°C).

TABLE 13: Annual energy consumption for heating before EEM

Annual energy consumption			
No.	Description	Value	Unit
1	Heat losses	12,017.4	Wat
2	Plant operating time (Continued use with reduction at night)	6	hour
3	Grade day	1,534	GRD
4	Design temperature difference	21.00	°C
5	Building surface	90.00	m ²
6	Annual thermal energy	5,267.06	kWh/a
	Annual specific consumption	58.52	kWh/m²a

As can be seen from the table above, based on the relevant data and calculations, the annual energy demand for heating of the building under analysis will be 5,267.06 kWh/a, with a specific consumption of 58.52 kWh/ m²a.

7. CURRENT ENERGETIC CLASSIFICATION OF THE APARTMENT

The measured energy consumption is not representative according to modern standards and comfort conditions. As there is currently no Albanian standard (fixing comfort requirements for lighting, hot sanitary water and heating) available the German ENEC standard was used to calculate the energy consumption baseline including comfort conditions.

The specific energy consumption of the building in the baseline case is 58.52 kWh/(m²a). Compared to the reference building defined in the German code the energy consumption of the present building is 153% lower.

FIGURE 13: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the reference building

FIGURE 14: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the reference building

8. MEASURES FOR INCREASING THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY CLASS

Energy efficiency describes the ratio between the benefit obtained and the energy used. From an economic point of view, energy efficiency can be described as the marginal productivity of energy input, specifying how much energy is needed to produce a given level of output (heat, light, motion, comfort).

FIGURE 15: Heat losses in a building from the envelope system

Main energy saving measures

- Insulation of walls and roofs/terraces
- Installation of energy efficient windows
- Installation of an energy efficient heating system
- Installation of an energy efficient cooling system
- Use of energy-efficient electric heaters
- Use of solar water heating systems
- Installation of an efficient lighting system
- Purchase of efficient household appliances

Below are the U values for the building structures according to the Decision No. 537, date 8.7.2020

TABLE 14: Comparison of U values for building structures

Building covering elements	Value U calculated (W/m ² K)	Comments	Maximum allowable U value as defined in the regulation U max (W/m ² K)	Legal basis
Exterior walls	1.488	Should be improved	0.40	DECISION No. 537, date 8.7.2020
Ceiling	1.650	In this case the ceiling communicates with the air-conditioned space above	0.35	
Floor	1.650	In this case the floor communicates with the air-conditioned space below	0.45	
Windows	7.00	Should be improved	2.20	

According to this Decision we can prove that all the U values calculated for this apartment are higher than the maximum allowable, so we must act on improvement of all building covering elements by reconfiguring the layers to improve the performance of envelope system.

8.1.1 Exterior wall insulation

Insulation of the exterior walls should be provided in case of reducing the value of the building heat loss in the heating and cooling conditions.

FIGURE 16: External wall insulation layers

TABLE 15: U-value, Exterior wall structure – proposed

Description: Exterior wall - Proposed						
Internal coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	8.1	Internal specific thermal resistance by convection m ²⁰ C/W		0.123		
External coefficient of heat transfer by convection [W/(m ² ·K)]:	23	External specific thermal resistance by convection (m ²⁰ C/W)		0.043		
Coefficient U [W/(m ² ·K)]:	0.386					
LAYERS						Thermal Resistance
Material	Thickness (δ)	Thermal conductivity coefficient (λ)	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Specific heat	Density	
(Description of wall structures from outside to inside)	[cm]	[W/(m·K)]	[W/(m ² ·K)]	[kJ/(kg·K)]	[kg/m ³]	[m ²⁰ C/W]
EIFS plaster	2.5	0.79	31.6		1,600	0.03
Insulation board + adhesive + reinforcing mesh	8	0.039	0.5		20	2.05
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Light weight concrete	12	0.29	2.4		800	0.41
Reinforced concrete slab	4	1.16	29.0		2,000	0.03
Gypsum plaster	2	0.9	45.0	0.91	1,800	0.02
The sum of the resistances (R)						2.588

FIGURE 17: Comparison of heat transmission coefficients for different thicknesses

8.1.1 Floor

The finish layer of the floor will be changed from ceramic tiles to laminate parquet for higher efficiency and thermal comfort.

8.1.2 Replacing Windows, Reducing the K coefficient

The windows in the apartment consist of none insulated aluminium frames with single glazed sliding panels. The thermal quality therefore is very poor. In conclusion, the improvement/replacement of the windows will be done for all apartment, in case to reduce the monthly bill (these windows with such elements reduce the infiltration of air and the loss of solar heat, reducing the amount of energy for heating and cooling the building).

Another small improvement can be the use of warm plastic spacers joining the glass pane instead of the typical aluminium option. The size of the gap between the glass is important too. Best windows offer 18mm space in the triple-glazed version and 24mm in double-glazed windows.

FIGURE 18: Single pane, double pane, and triple pane glass window

TABLE 19
Overall U-factors (heat transfer coefficients) for various windows and skylights in W/m² · °C (from ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamentals, Chap. 27, Table 5)

Type	Glass section (glazing) only		Aluminum frame (without thermal break)			Wood or vinyl frame						
	Center-of-glass	Edge-of-glass	Fixed	Double door	Sloped skylight	Fixed	Double door		Sloped skylight			
Frame width →	(Not applicable)		32 mm (1 1/4 in)	53 mm (2 in)	19 mm (3/4 in)	41 mm (1 1/4 in)	88 mm (3 7/16 in)		23 mm (1 in)			
Spacer type →	—	Metal Insul.	All	All	All	Metal Insul.	Metal Insul.	Metal Insul.	Metal Insul.	Metal Insul.		
Glazing Type												
Single Glazing												
3 mm (1/8 in) glass	6.30	6.30	—	6.63	7.16	9.88	5.93	—	5.57	—	7.57	—
6.4 mm (1/4 in) acrylic	5.28	5.28	—	5.69	6.27	8.86	5.02	—	4.77	—	6.57	—
3 mm (1/8 in) acrylic	5.79	5.79	—	6.16	6.71	9.94	5.48	—	5.17	—	7.63	—
Double Glazing (no coating)												
6.4 mm air space	3.24	3.71	3.34	3.90	4.55	6.70	3.26	3.16	3.20	3.09	4.37	4.22
12.7 mm air space	2.78	3.40	2.91	3.51	4.18	6.65	2.88	2.76	2.86	2.74	4.32	4.17
6.4 mm argon space	2.95	3.52	3.07	3.66	4.32	6.47	3.03	2.91	2.98	2.87	4.14	3.97
12.7 mm argon space	2.61	3.28	2.76	3.36	4.04	6.47	2.74	2.61	2.73	2.60	4.14	3.97
Double Glazing [ε = 0.1, coating on one of the surfaces of air space (surface 2 or 3, counting from the outside toward inside)]												
6.4 mm air space	2.44	3.16	2.60	3.21	3.89	6.04	2.59	2.46	2.60	2.47	3.73	3.53
12.7 mm air space	1.82	2.71	2.06	2.67	3.37	6.04	2.06	1.92	2.13	1.99	3.73	3.53
6.4 mm argon space	1.99	2.83	2.21	2.82	3.52	5.62	2.21	2.07	2.26	2.12	3.32	3.09
12.7 mm argon space	1.53	2.49	1.83	2.42	3.14	5.71	1.82	1.67	1.91	1.78	3.41	3.19
Triple Glazing (no coating)												
6.4 mm air space	2.16	2.96	2.35	2.97	3.66	5.81	2.34	2.18	2.36	2.21	3.48	3.24
12.7 mm air space	1.76	2.67	2.02	2.62	3.33	5.67	2.01	1.84	2.07	1.91	3.34	3.09
6.4 mm argon space	1.93	2.79	2.16	2.77	3.47	5.57	2.15	1.99	2.19	2.04	3.25	3.00
12.7 mm argon space	1.65	2.58	1.92	2.52	3.23	5.53	1.91	1.74	1.98	1.82	3.20	2.95
Triple Glazing [ε = 0.1, coating on one of the surfaces of air spaces (surfaces 3 and 5, counting from the outside toward inside)]												
6.4 mm air space	1.53	2.49	1.83	2.42	3.14	5.24	1.81	1.64	1.89	1.73	2.92	2.66
12.7 mm air space	0.97	2.05	1.38	1.92	2.66	5.10	1.33	1.15	1.46	1.30	2.78	2.52
6.4 mm argon space	1.19	2.23	1.56	2.12	2.85	4.90	1.52	1.35	1.64	1.47	2.59	2.33
12.7 mm argon space	0.80	1.92	1.25	1.77	2.51	4.86	1.18	1.01	1.33	1.17	2.55	2.28

TABLE 16: Overall U-value for various windows (according to ASHRAE Handbook of Fundamentals)

The type of window that we have selected for the replacement of the old ones is the one significant in the red square.

8.1.1 Replacing the lighting system

The following measures are recommended:

- Replacing the incandescent and fluorescent lamps (CFL) currently installed with LED lamps ensuring also the actual required illumination value.

FIGURE 19: Energy saving vs Energy consumption on lighting systems

8.1.1 Increasing the efficiency of the heating/cooling system

The new system selected for heating and cooling this apartment must belong to class A of energy efficiency, with the Energy Efficiency Ratio EER > 3.2 and the Coefficient of Performance COP > 3.6.

9. THERMAL LOSS CALCULATIONS

TABLE 17: Heat losses in the winter period after AEE (referring to the table no.18)

Heat losses from building envelope (Wat)							
Air infiltrations	Floor	Terrace	Walls	Doors and Windows	Thermal node	Correction factor	Total heat losses (W)
5,239.1	445.5	445.5	787.9	321.9	187.6	891.3	8,318.8

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TABLE 18: Heat losses calculation of the building after EEM

HEAT LOSSES CALCULATIONS OF THE BUILDING AFTER EEM																		
Structures	Volume of heating spaces	ORIENTATION	Heat transfer coefficient (k)	Length	Height	Surface	Surface which need to be deduced	The outer surface of the structure	Desired indoor temperature (tb)	Outside temperature (tj)	Heat losses (Qt)	Heat losses in the nodes (Qn)	Heat losses (Orientation supplements)		Heat losses from the air infiltrations		Total heat losses	
	m3		W/m ² ·K	m	m	m ²	m ²	m ²	°C	°C	W	W	%	W	naj	W	W	
Exterior wall	252.0	N	0.386	10.94	2.80	30.63	4.5	26.13	21	0	211.8	21.2	20	42.4	3	5239.1	275.4	
Exterior wall		S	0.386	10.94	2.80	30.63	4.5	26.13	21	0	211.8	21.2	10	21.2			254.2	
Exterior wall		W	0.386	4.90	2.80	13.72	2.0	11.74	21	0	95.2	9.5	15	14.3			119.0	
Interior wall		W	1.455	5.00	2.80	14.00	0.0	14.00	21	18	61.1	6.1	15	9.2			76.4	
Interior wall		E	1.455	9.90	2.80	27.72	0.0	27.72	21	18	121.0	12.1	0	0.0			133.1	
Window		N	1.150	3.00	1.50	4.50	0.0	4.50	21	0	108.7	10.9	20	21.7			141.3	
Window		S	1.150	3.00	1.50	4.50	0.0	4.50	21	0	108.7	10.9	15	16.3			135.8	
Exterior door		W	1.6	0.90	2.20	1.98	0.0	1.98	21	0	66.5	6.7	0	0.0			73.2	
Floor				1.650	-	-	90.00	0.0	90.00	21	18	445.5	44.6	0			0.0	490.1
Terrace				1.650	-	-	90.00	0.0	90.00	21	18	445.5	44.6	0			0.0	490.1
																	Qtot	7,427.5
															Gv	0.41	W/m ³ °C	
SURFACE 90 M2							Corrections in percentage (%) for intermittent operation and load reduction									891.3	W	
							Continued use with reduction at night - Plant with warm air 12%											
S/V =	0.36															8,318.8	W	

Based on the previous information's, part of the DCM No.38, date 16.01.2003 through interpolation we derive that for the report $\frac{S}{V} = 0.36$ of our building is the same as before, the normative coefficient for the allow volume heat loss its $G_{vt0} = 1.58 \text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

From heat losses calculation shown in above table, the new volume heat loss coefficient with transmission for the building analysed is $G_{vt} = 1.57 \text{ W/m}^3\text{°C}$.

In our case: $G_{vt} \leq G_{vt0}$

As conclusion we can state that analyses building after EEM fulfils the Albanian legal requirements for the heat losses in the building.

Note: G_{vt} is lower than G_{vt0} which is conform the condition recommended by the DCM No..38.

10. ENERGETIC CLASSIFICATION OF THE APARTMENT AFTER EEM

TABLE 19: Annual energy consumption for heating before EEM

Annual energy consumption			
No.	Description	Value	Unit
1	Heat losses	8,318.8	Wat
2	Plant operating time (Continued use with reduction at night)	6	hour
3	Grade day	1,534	GRD
4	Design temperature difference	21.00	°C
5	Building surface	90.00	m ²
6	Annual thermal energy	3,646.01	kWh/a
	Annual specific consumption	40.51	kWh/m²a

FIGURE 20: Classification of the baseline case regarding to the new building conditions

FIGURE 21: Classification of Energy Class regarding to the Albanian Law

11. COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

The estimated costs of the structural and comfort measures are based on official cost tables provided by the Ministry of Transport & Infrastructure¹ and on Albanian market prices.

The costs are estimated for the structural measures which are fundamental and should be realized before or in combination with further energy efficiency measures.

TABLE 20: Electrical consumption and costs before EEM

¹ REF. [28] Technical Manuals MD 2012, Official Bulletin 83- 2012, <http://www.mppt.gov.al/>

Electrical consumption before EEM							
Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	Incandescent	1	65	0.065	12	0.78	284.70
Living room	Incandescent	2	65	0.13	12	1.56	569.40
Toilet	fluorescent	2	32	0.064	12	0.768	280.32
Bedroom 1	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Bedroom 2	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Bedroom 3	fluorescent	2	60	0.12	12	1.44	525.60
Corridor	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Balcony	fluorescent	1	32	0.032	12	0.384	140.16
Total				0.683		8.196	2,991.54
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							54.39
Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Heating/cooling capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Single-split air conditioner	3.4/3.2 kW	4	1,200.00	4.80	6	28.8	10,512.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							191.13
Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	2,500.00	2.5	12	30	10,950.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							199.09
Total Electrical Annual consumption (kWh/a)							24,453.54
The price of electricity (euro/kWh)							0.14
Total price of Electrical Annual consumption before EEM (euro)							3,423.50

TABLE 21: Electrical consumption and costs after EEM

Electrical consumption after EEM							
Lighting Consumption Per Premise and Type of Lighting							
Premises	Type of lighting	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Kitchen	LED	1	20	0.02	12	0.24	87.60
Living room	LED	1	30	0.03	12	0.36	131.40
Toilet	LED	1	10	0.01	12	0.12	43.80
Bedroom 1	LED	1	15	0.015	12	0.18	65.70
Bedroom 2	LED	1	15	0.015	12	0.18	65.70
Bedroom 3	LED	1	15	0.015	12	0.18	65.70
Corridor	LED	1	10	0.01	12	0.12	43.80
Balcony	LED	1	5	0.005	12	0.06	21.90
Total				0.12		1.44	525.60
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							9.56
Heating/cooling System Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Annual consumption (kWh/a)			COP		Annual consumption (kWh/a)	
Single-split air conditioner	7,292.0			3.8		1,918.95	
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							34.89
Sanitary Hot Water Consumption Per Premise							
Equipment	Capacity	Qty	Power per unit (W/unit)	Total power (kW)	Working hours	Daily consumption (kWh/d)	Annual consumption (kWh/a)
Electric boiler	100 liter	1	1,200.00	1.2	12	14.4	5,256.00
Specific electrical energy (kWh/m²a)							95.56
ELECTRICAL COST							
Total Electrical Annual consumption (kWh/a)							7,700.55
The price of electricity (euro/kWh)							0.14
Total price of Electrical Annual consumption after EEM(euro)							1,078.08

TABLE 22: Total investment value for EEM

Building Envelope Measures	Unit	Qty	Unit price [€]	Investment Cost [€]
Preparation for the EE Measures (demolition, transportation, cleaning up)	m ²	90.00	10 €	900.00 €
External wall envelope (thermal insulation EPS thickness 8 cm)	m ²	52.00	25.00 €	1,300.00 €

Windows Renewal ≤ 1.4 W/m ² K	m ²	9.00	140.00 €	1,260.00 €
Laminate floor 0.8 cm	m ²	90.00	15.00 €	1,350.00 €
TOTAL COSTS 1 (€)				4,810.00 €
Other EE Measures	Unit	Qty	Unit price [€]	Investment Cost [€]
Heating/cooling Air Condition system	pcs	4.00	650 €	2,600 €
DHW: 50% Solar Thermal Panels + 50% Air Heat Pumps	pcs	-	-	750.00 €
Photovoltaic panels	pcs	-	-	882.00 €
Lighting (CFL + LED)	pcs	8.00	80 €	640 €
TOTAL COSTS 2 (€)				4,872.00 €
TOTAL COSTS without Solar and photovoltaic panels [1+2] (€)				8,050.00 €
TOTAL COSTS with Solar and photovoltaic panels [1+2] (€)				9,682.00 €

TABLE 23: Savings and investment repayment time

Price of Electrical Annual consumption before EEM (euro)	Price of Electrical Annual consumption after EEM (euro)	Annual savings (euro)	Total Investment value (euro)	Payback period (years)
3,423.50 €	1,078.08 €	2,345.42 €	8,050.00 €	3.4

12. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Analysis done for the baseline show that the apartment taken in analyse has an energy consumption of **58.52 kWh/m²a**, classifying in **ENERGY CLASSES C**, which according to the **Albanian law (*Law no. 116 date 10.11.2016 for Energy Efficiency in Buildings*)**.

In based of such analysis its recommended to be done some interventions which will bring the apartment **40.51 kWh/m²a**, in **ENERGY CLASSES B**, fulfilling the requirements of Albanian law.

Needed interventions:

- Insulation for the entire building envelope
- Replacing the lighting system from CFL and Incandescent lights to LED
- Replacing the electric boiler from standard on/off to smart boilers that saves up to 20% energy
- Replacement of the old mono-split heating/cooling non inverter to new equipment's with higher performance and inverter

Further recommendations for increasing the **ENERGY CLASSES** from **B** to **A**:

- Replacing the electric boilers with solar panels for generating hot sanitary water
- Installation of photovoltaic panels to save electrical energy and use of its energy for heating/cooling system.

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Co-Plan
Tirana, Albania

Project Name: GreenFORCE, Foster Research Excellence for
Green Transition in the Western Balkans

6/10/2024

Your PV system

Address of Installation

Project Overview

Figure: Overview Image, 3D Design

PV System

3D, Grid-connected PV system with Electrical Appliances and Thermal System

Climate Data	Tirana, ALB (1996 - 2015)
PV Generator Output	58.8 kWp
PV Generator Surface	306.0 m ²
Number of PV Modules	168
Number of Inverters	6

Figure: Schematic diagram

The yield

The yield

PV Generator Energy (AC grid)	77,981 kWh
Direct Own Use	41,412 kWh
Grid Feed-in	35,052 kWh
Heat pump	1,517 kWh
Down-regulation at Feed-in Point	0 kWh
Own Power Consumption	54.8 %
Solar Fraction	20.4 %
Spec. Annual Yield	1,319.63 kWh/kWp
Performance Ratio (PR)	85.8 %
Yield Reduction due to Shading	Not calculated
CO ₂ Emissions avoided	36,469 kg / year

Thermal system

Overview

Total heat demand	25054 kWh
Hot water demand	25054 kWh
Storage tank: Volume	2000 liter
Heat pump: Nominal heating output	25 kW
Boiler: Type of boiler	Gas

Financial Analysis

Your Gain

Total investment costs	58,800.00 \$
Internal Rate of Return of Capital Resources	27.22 %
Minimum System Operating Period	6.3 Years
Electricity Production Costs	0.06 \$/kWh
Energy Balance/Feed-in Concept	Net-Metering

The results have been calculated with a mathematical model calculation from Valentin Software GmbH (PV*SOL algorithms). The actual yields from the solar power system may differ as a result of weather variations, the efficiency of the modules and inverter, and other factors.

Set-up of the System

Overview

System Data

Type of System	3D, Grid-connected PV system with Electrical Appliances and Thermal System
Start of Operation	6/10/2024

Climate Data

Location	Tirana, ALB (1996 - 2015)
Resolution of the data	1 h
Simulation models used:	
- Diffuse Irradiation onto Horizontal Plane	Hofmann
- Irradiance onto tilted surface	Hay & Davies

Consumption

Total Consumption	203760 kWh
2-person household with 2 children	172320 kWh
Heat Pump System with Space Heating and Domestic Hot Water (air/water)	31440 kWh
Load Peak	398.3 kW

Module Areas

1. Module Area - Building 03-Roof Area South

PV Generator, 1. Module Area - Building 03-Roof Area South

Name	Building 03-Roof Area South
PV Modules	168 x Vitovolt 300 M350 AI - allblack (v1)
Manufacturer	Viessmann Climate Solutions SE
Inclination	0 °
Orientation	South 180 °
Installation Type	Mounted - Open Space
PV Generator Surface	306.0 m ²

Figure: 1. Module Area - Building 03-Roof Area South

Horizon Line, 3D Design

Figure: Horizon (3D Design)

Inverter configuration

Configuration 1

Module Area	Building 03-Roof Area South
Inverter 1	
Model	Vitocharge VX3, Typ 8.0A (PV+BAT) (v2)
Manufacturer	Viessmann Climate Solutions SE
Quantity	6
Sizing Factor	122.5 %
Configuration	MPP 1: 1 x 14 MPP 2: 1 x 14

AC Mains

AC Mains

Number of Phases	3
Mains Voltage (1-phase)	230 V
Displacement Power Factor (cos phi)	+/- 1

Thermal system

Overview

Total heat demand	25054 kWh
Hot water demand	25054 kWh
Specific heat demand	200 kWh/m ²

Storage tank

Volume	2000 liter
Thickness of insulation	100 mm
Temperature of the storage environment	15 °C
Max. Storage tank temperature by boiler	60 °C
Max. Storage tank temperature through heating element	70 °C
Legionella protection	
Storage tank temperature	60 °C
Time	14:00
Interval	Daily

Heat generators

Heat pump	
Type	25 kW, COP 3.1
Type of Operation	Standard
Nominal heating output	25 kW
Boiler	
Type of boiler	Gas

Heat consumers

Hot water	
Annual consumption	25054 kWh

Simulation Results

Results Total System

PV System

PV Generator Output	58.8 kWp
Spec. Annual Yield	1,319.63 kWh/kWp
Performance Ratio (PR)	85.8 %
Yield Reduction due to Shading	Not calculated
PV Generator Energy (AC grid)	77,981 kWh/Year
Heat pump	1,517 kWh/Year
Down-regulation at Feed-in Point	0 kWh/Year
CO ₂ Emissions avoided	36,469 kg / year

PV Generator Energy (AC grid)

Appliances

Appliances	203,760 kWh/Year
Standby Consumption (Inverter)	386 kWh/Year
Heat pump	5,777 kWh/Year
Total Consumption	209,923 kWh/Year
Energy from Grid	131,942.9 kWh
Solar Fraction	37.1 %

Total heat demand

Thermal system

Hot water demand	25,054 kWh/Year
Thermal losses	1,581 kWh/Year
Total heat demand	26,635 kWh/Year
covered by boiler	64 kWh/Year
covered by heat pump	26,572 kWh/Year
Electrical energy consumption of the heat pump	5,777 kWh/Year
of which is solar	1,517 kWh/Year
Solar Fraction (Thermal system)	26.2 %
CO ₂ Emissions avoided	4,109 kg / year

Level of Self-sufficiency

Total Consumption	209,923 kWh/Year
covered by grid	166,995 kWh/Year
Level of Self-sufficiency	20.4 %

Energy Flow Graph

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All values in kWh
Small deviations in the totals can occur due to rounding
created with PV*SOL.

Figure: Energy Flow Graph

Figure: Thermal system

Financial Analysis

Overview

System Data

PV Generator Energy (AC grid)	77,981 kWh/Year
PV Generator Output	58.8 kWp
Start of Operation of the System	6/10/2024
Assessment Period	20 Years
Interest on Capital	1 %

Economic Parameters

Internal Rate of Return of Capital Resources	27.22 %
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance)	166,815.88 \$
Minimum System Operating Period	6.3 Years
Electricity Production Costs	0.06 \$/kWh

Payment Overview

Specific Investment Costs	1,000.00 \$/kWp
Investment Costs	58,800.00 \$
One-off Payments	0.00 \$
Incoming Subsidies	0.00 \$
Annual Costs	1,000.00 \$/Year
Other Revenue or Savings	0.00 \$/Year

Loans

Reference	Loan 1
Loan Capital	35,280.00 \$
Payment Installment	100.00 %
Credit type	Installment Loan
Term	8.00 Years
Grace period	1.00 Year
Interest	4.00
Repayment Period	Annually

Remuneration and Savings

Total Payment from Utility in First Year	0.00 \$/Year
First year savings	10,863.22 \$/Year
New Tariff (OSHEE)	
Energy Price	0.14 \$/kWh
Base Price	42.00 \$/Month
Compensation for Surplus	0.00 \$/kWh
Inflation Rate for Energy Price	2 %/Year

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Figure: Electricity cost saving

Figure: Electricity Cost Trend (Price Increase Rate 2 %)

Cash flow

Cashflow Table

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Operating costs	(\$990.10)	(\$980.30)	(\$970.59)	(\$960.98)	(\$951.47)
Self-Financing	(\$23,520.00)	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Savings on energy costs	\$10,646.33	\$10,862.15	\$10,969.70	\$11,078.31	\$11,188.00
Loan repayments	\$0.00	(\$4,940.69)	(\$4,891.77)	(\$4,843.34)	(\$4,795.39)
Loan Interest	(\$1,397.23)	(\$1,383.39)	(\$1,174.03)	(\$968.67)	(\$767.26)
Annual Cash Flow	(\$15,260.99)	\$3,557.77	\$3,933.31	\$4,305.32	\$4,673.88
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance)	(\$15,260.99)	(\$11,703.22)	(\$7,769.91)	(\$3,464.59)	\$1,209.29
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance) minus pending loans	(\$54,260.70)	(\$44,378.84)	(\$34,379.73)	(\$24,262.40)	(\$14,025.86)

	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
Operating costs	(\$942.05)	(\$932.72)	(\$923.48)	(\$914.34)	(\$905.29)
Self-Financing	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Savings on energy costs	\$11,298.77	\$11,410.63	\$11,523.62	\$11,637.71	\$11,752.94
Loan repayments	(\$4,747.91)	(\$4,700.90)	(\$4,654.36)	\$0.00	\$0.00
Loan Interest	(\$569.75)	(\$376.07)	(\$186.17)	\$0.00	\$0.00
Annual Cash Flow	\$5,039.07	\$5,400.95	\$5,759.61	\$10,723.37	\$10,847.65
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance)	\$6,248.36	\$11,649.31	\$17,408.92	\$28,132.28	\$38,979.94
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance) minus pending loans	(\$3,669.14)	\$6,808.78	\$17,408.92	\$28,132.28	\$38,979.94

	Year 11	Year 12	Year 13	Year 14	Year 15
Operating costs	(\$896.32)	(\$887.45)	(\$878.66)	(\$869.96)	(\$861.35)
Self-Financing	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Savings on energy costs	\$11,869.30	\$11,986.82	\$12,105.50	\$12,225.36	\$12,346.40
Loan repayments	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Loan Interest	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Annual Cash Flow	\$10,972.97	\$11,099.37	\$11,226.84	\$11,355.40	\$11,485.05
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance)	\$49,952.91	\$61,052.28	\$72,279.12	\$83,634.51	\$95,119.57
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance) minus pending loans	\$49,952.91	\$61,052.28	\$72,279.12	\$83,634.51	\$95,119.57

	Year 16	Year 17	Year 18	Year 19	Year 20
Operating costs	(\$852.82)	(\$844.38)	(\$836.02)	(\$827.74)	(\$819.54)
Self-Financing	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Savings on energy costs	\$12,468.64	\$12,592.10	\$12,716.76	\$12,842.67	\$12,969.83
Loan repayments	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Loan Interest	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
Annual Cash Flow	\$11,615.82	\$11,747.72	\$11,880.75	\$12,014.93	\$12,150.29
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance)	\$106,735.39	\$118,483.10	\$130,363.85	\$142,378.79	\$154,529.07
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance) minus pending loans	\$106,735.39	\$118,483.10	\$130,363.85	\$142,378.79	\$154,529.07

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	Year 21
Operating costs	(\$811.43)
Self-Financing	\$0.00
Savings on energy costs	\$13,098.24
Loan repayments	\$0.00
Loan Interest	\$0.00
Annual Cash Flow	\$12,286.81
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance)	\$166,815.88
Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance) minus pending loans	\$166,815.88

Degradation and inflation rates are applied on a monthly basis over the entire observation period. This is done in the first year.

Figure: Accrued Cash Flow (Cash Balance)

Energy Supply Account

Energy Supply Account

Reference	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun
Consumption	21732.72	18907.48	18024.23	16322.78	15485.64	14253.43
Energy production	2629.14	3744.77	6293.76	7356.65	9619.76	10771.11
Energy production (incl. Degradation of Module)	2629.14	3744.77	6293.76	7356.65	9619.76	10771.11
Balance	19103.58	15162.71	11730.48	8966.13	5865.89	3482.32

Savings	2629.14	3744.77	6293.76	7356.65	9619.76	10771.11
Value in kWh						

Costs without solar energy system	3129.24	2733.71	2610.05	2371.85	2254.65	2082.14
Costs with solar energy system	2761.16	2209.44	1728.93	1341.92	907.88	574.18
Cost savings	368.08	524.27	881.13	1029.93	1346.77	1507.96
Value in \$						

Reference	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Consumption	15790.04	15637.73	15652.04	17360.89	18749.71	21620.57
Energy production	10835.18	9496.51	6855.90	5107.91	2760.82	2122.92
Energy production (incl. Degradation of Module)	10835.18	9496.51	6855.90	5107.91	2760.82	2122.92
Balance	4954.87	6141.23	8796.14	12252.98	15988.89	19497.65

Savings	10835.18	9496.51	6855.90	5107.91	2760.82	2122.92
Value in kWh						

Costs without solar energy system	2297.27	2275.94	2277.95	2517.18	2711.62	3113.54
Costs with solar energy system	780.34	946.43	1318.12	1802.08	2325.10	2816.33
Cost savings	1516.92	1329.51	959.83	715.11	386.51	297.21
Value in \$						

Reference	Total
Consumption	209537.28
Energy production	77594.43
Energy production (incl. Degradation of Module)	77594.43
Balance	131942.86

Savings	77594.43
Value in kWh	

Costs without solar energy system	30375.13
Costs with solar energy system	19511.91
Cost savings	10863.22
Value in \$	

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Degradation and inflation rates are applied on a monthly basis over the entire observation period. This is done in the first year.

Plans and parts list

Circuit Diagram

Figure: Circuit Diagram

Dimensioning Plan

Figure: Building 03-Roof Area South

String Plan

Figure: Building 03-Roof Area South

Parts list

Parts list

#	Type	Item number	Manufacturer	Name	Quantity	Unit
1	PV Module		Viessmann Climate Solutions SE	Vitovolt 300 M350 AI - allblack	168	Piece
2	Inverter		Viessmann Climate Solutions SE	Vitocharge VX3, Typ 8.0A (PV+BAT)	6	Piece
3	Components			Feed-In Meter	1	Piece
4	Components			Bidirectional Meter	1	Piece
5	Components			House connection	1	Piece

Greenforce_Building 3

Results of annual simulation

Installed collector power:		20.950 kW
Installed solar surface area (gross):		50.2 m ²
Irradiation on collector surface (active):	81,314.88 kWh	1,744.96 kWh/m ²
Energy delivered by collectors:	41,218.27 kWh	884.51 kWh/m ²
Energy delivered by collector loop:	40,782.09 kWh	875.15 kWh/m ²
DHW heating energy supply:		62,634.92 kWh
Solar energy contribution to DHW:		39,964.19 kWh
Energy from auxiliary heating:		24,589.6 kWh
Electricity savings:		0.0 kWh
CO2 emissions avoided:		10,646.46 kg
DHW solar fraction:		61.9 %
Relative savings of supplementary energy (DIN EN 12977):		62.3 %
System efficiency:		49.1 %

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-Tirana, Albania

Greenforce_Building 3

Site Data

Climate data

Location:	Tirana
Climate data record:	Tirana
Total annual global irradiation:	1554.253 kWh/m ²
Latitude:	41.33 °
Longitude:	-19.78 °

Domestic hot water

Average daily consumption:	4.4 m ³
Desired temperature:	50 °C
Consumption profile:	Detached house (evening max)
Cold water temperature:	February: 13.5 °C August: 19 °C
Circulation:	no

-Studio Archimed Shpk

-Tirana, Albania

Greenforce_Building 3

System

Collector loop

Manufacturer:	Viessmann Werke GmbH & Co KG
Type:	Vitosol 100-FM SV1F
Number:	20.00
Total gross surface area:	50.2 m ²
Total active solar surface area:	46.6 m ²
Inclination (Tilt Angle):	30 °
Orientation:	180 °
Azimuth:	0 °

DHW standby tank

Manufacturer:	Viessmann
Type:	DHW standby tank
Volume:	2 m ³

Solar preheating tank

Manufacturer:	Viessmann
Type:	Solar preheating tank
Volume:	3 m ³

Auxiliary heating

Manufacturer:	Standard
Type:	Heat pump
Nominal output:	25 kW

Solar energy consumption as percentage of total consumption

Daily maximum collector temperature

These calculations were carried out by T*SOL 2023 (R2) - the simulation program for solar thermal heating systems. The results are determined by a mathematical model calculation with variable time steps of up to 6 minutes. Actual yields can deviate from these values due to fluctuations in climate, consumption and other factors. The system schematic diagram above does not represent and cannot replace a full technical drawing of the solar system.

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Photo Plan

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-Tirana, Albania

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Financial analysis

System

Active solar surface:	46.6 m ²
System yield:	39,964.19 kWh
Annual fuel savings:	15,985.7 kWh Electricity

Financial analysis parameters

Life span:	20 Years
Interest on capital:	2.5 %
Reinvestment return:	2.5 %
Energy cost escalation rate:	2.0 %
Running cost escalation rate:	1.0 %

Financing

Total investments:	50,000 \$
Subsidies:	0 \$
Loan capital:	30,000 \$
Remaining investment:	20,000 \$

Loan ref:	Bank
Loan capital:	30,000 \$
Period/(loan interest):	8 Years / 4.5 %
Annual installment:	5,091 \$
Grade Period:	1

Running costs in first year:	1,024 \$
Savings in first year:	8,632 \$

Financial analysis

Cost of solar energy:	0.113 \$/kWh
Capital return time:	5.6 Years
Amortization period:	7.2 Years

Profitability

Return on assets:	300.4 %
Return on equity:	751.0 %
Internal rate of return rate, IRR:	23.67 %
Net present value:	90,559 \$

Reinvestment premise

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Profit: 161,163 \$
Modified internal rate of return, MIRR: 11.65 %

Energy balance schematic

Legend

1	Irradiation on collector surface (active)	81,315 kWh
1.1	Optical collector losses	20,230 kWh
1.2	Thermal collector losses	19,867 kWh
2	Energy from collector array	41,218 kWh
2.2	Solar energy to preheating tank	40,782 kWh
2.5	Internal piping losses	324 kWh
2.6	External piping losses	112 kWh
3.1	Tank losses	1,914 kWh
3.3	Preheating tank to tank	39,964 kWh
4.1	Tank losses (S)	825 kWh
6	Final energy	9,836 kWh
6.1	Supplementary energy to tank	24,590 kWh
9	DHW energy from tank	62,635 kWh

Glossary

- 1 Irradiation on collector surface (active)
Solar energy irradiated onto tilted collector area (active surface area)
- 1.1 Optical collector losses
Reflection and other losses
- 1.2 Thermal collector losses
Heat conduction and other losses
- 2 Energy from collector array
Energy output at collector array outlet (i.e. before piping)
- 2.2 Solar energy to preheating tank
Collector array energy minus piping losses
- 2.5 Internal piping losses
Internal piping losses
- 2.6 External piping losses
External piping losses
- 3.1 Tank losses
Heat losses via surface area
- 3.3 Preheating tank to tank
Heat from preheating tank to tank
- 4.1 Tank losses (S)
Heat losses via surface area
- 6 Final energy
Final energy supply to system. This can be supplied from natural gas, oil or electricity (not including solar energy) and takes efficiency into account.
- 6.1 Supplementary energy to tank
Supplementary energy (e.g. boiler) to tank
- 9 DHW energy from tank
Heat from tank (excluding circulation) for DHW consumption

Climate

Data record:	Tirana
Location:	Tirana
Latitude:	41.33 °
Longitude:	-19.78 °
Total annual global irradiation:	1,554 kWh/m ²
Diffuse radiation percentage:	45.6 %
Mean outside temperature:	16.17 °C

Hot water consumption

DHW consumption

Average daily consumption:	4.400 m ³
Annual consumption:	1,606.0 m ³
Max daily consumption:	5.200 m ³
Desired temperature:	50.0 °C
Cold water temperature:	13.5 °C / 19.0 °C
Annual energy requirement:	62,458 kWh
Days in operation:	365 Days
Not operating:	-No limitation-

Circulation

- no circulation present -

Consumption profile

Profile:	Detached house (evening max)
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Collector loop (CL 1)

Volume flow:	40 l/h
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-Tirana, Albania

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Heat transfer medium: water with 40 % Polypropylene glycol
Heat capacity: 3588 J/(kg*K)

Control:

The collector loop pump control is dependent on the difference between the collector outlet temperature and the tank reference temperature.

Switch on above a difference of: 8 K

Switch off below a difference of: 3 K

Collector array

Total gross surface area 50.2 m²

Total active solar surface area 46.6 m²

Number of collectors: 20

Installation:

Inclination (Tilt Angle): 30 °

Azimuth angle: 0 °

Irradiation on collector surface (gross): 87,597 kWh

Piping:

One-way length of piping system

inside: 8 m

outside: 1 m

between collectors: 200 mm/Collector

Thermal conductivity of insulation

inside: 0.045 W/(m·K)

outside: 0.045 W/(m·K)

between collectors: 0.045 W/(m·K)

Nominal diameter of piping

inside and outside: 40 mm

between collectors: 25 mm

(Corresponds to a flow velocity of approx 0.5 m/s)

Insulation thickness

inside: 40 mm

outside: 40 mm

between collectors: 30 mm

Flat-plate collector

Manufacturer: Viessmann Werke GmbH & Co
KG
Type: Vitosol 100-FM SV1F

Heat capacity:

Specific heat capacity: 5330 J/(m²*K)

Losses:

Conversion factor: 80.6 %
Simple heat transfer coefficient: 3.816 W/(m²K)
Quadratic heat transfer coefficient: 0.045 W/(m²K²)
The characteristic has two sections.
Switch over temperature: 50 °C
Simple heat transfer coefficient (2): 5.977 W/(m²K)
Quadratic heat transfer coefficient (2): 0.009 W/(m²K²)
Heat transfer coefficients based on collector flow temperature: No
Incident angle modifier (IAM) for diffuse radiation: 91.1 %
Incident angle modifier for direct irradiation
with an incident angle of 50°: 89.4 %

Size:

Gross surface: 2.51 m²
Active solar surface: 2.33 m² (Gross surface)

DHW standby tank

Manufacturer: Viessmann
Type: DHW standby tank
Volume: 2000 l
Height/Diameter: 1.80
Number of tanks: 1

Insulation:

Insulation thickness: 100 mm
Thermal conductivity: 0.065 W/(m*K)

Connections:

	Height:	Losses:
Upper tank outlet:	100 %	0.25 W/K
Lower tank inlet:	0 %	0.25 W/K
Circulation return:	-without-	
Heat exchanger Auxiliary heating:		

	Height:	Losses:
Return:	2 %	0.25 W/K
Supply:	60 %	0.25 W/K

Heat exchanger:

kA value Auxiliary heating: 1 W/K per tank volume

Control:

Desired tank temperature:		Desired DHW temp + 0 K
Limited load times:		none
	Height:	Switching temp.:
Switch on auxiliary heating:	30 %	-3 K
Switch off auxiliary heating:	30 %	3 K

Solar preheating tank

Manufacturer:	Viessmann
Type:	Solar preheating tank
Volume:	3000 l
Height/Diameter:	1.80
Number of tanks:	1

Insulation:

Insulation thickness	100 mm
Thermal conductivity:	0.065 W/(m·K)

Connections:

	Height:	Losses:
Upper tank outlet:	100 %	0.25 W/K
Lower tank inlet:	0 %	0.25 W/K
Circulation return:	-without-	
Heat exchanger Collector loop connection		

	Height:	Losses:
Return:	2 %	0.25 W/K

Greenforce_Building 3

Supply: 60 % 0.25 W/K

Heat exchanger:

kA value Collector loop connection: 1 W/K per tank volume

Control:

Desired tank temperature: Desired DHW temp + 0 K

Limited load times: none

Collector loop - switch on/off: Height: Switching temp.:

Switch off collector loop: 19 %

90 % 90 °C

Heat pump

Manufacturer: Standard

Type: Heat pump

Nominal output: 25.0 kW

Boiler type: modulating boiler

Temperature range: 5 K / 20 K / 40 K

Return mixing valve: none

Energy source: Electricity

Efficiency: 250 %

with a return temperature of: 95 °C

Efficiency: 250 %

with a return temperature of: 30 °C

Efficiency of domestic hot water supply: 250 %

Efficiency based on the higher heating value (HHV), Hs: 250 %

with a return temperature of: 95 °C

Efficiency based on the higher heating value (HHV), Hs: 250 %

with a return temperature of: 30 °C

Efficiency of DHW supply, Hs: 250 %

Hi (LHV): 0.001 kJ/kWh

Not operating: -No limitation-

Results of annual simulation

Year	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
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DHW system (2 tanks)

Savings Electricity in

CO2 emissions avoided in kg

10,646.5	502.8	630.3	959.6	956.1	1,126.3	1,213.1	1,124.5	1,204.5	1,033.3	917.0	567.1	411.9
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DHW solar fraction in %

61.9	29.4	40.1	60.5	64.2	85.2	96.5	99.5	97.2	85.6	64.8	35.9	24.4
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System efficiency in %

49.2	48.4	50.3	51.5	50.3	48.8	48.0	43.1	48.3	52.0	52.8	51.9	48.2
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Solar energy contribution to DHW in kWh

39,964	1,887	2,366	3,602	3,589	4,228	4,554	4,221	4,521	3,879	3,442	2,129	1,546
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E Solar loop to tank in kWh

40,782	1,882	2,394	3,622	3,653	4,336	4,730	4,411	4,682	3,917	3,494	2,125	1,535
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Energy: Aux. heating in kWh

24,590	4,536	3,542	2,351	2,001	737	166	23	130	653	1,870	3,802	4,780
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Climate

Outside temperature in °C

16.2	6.8	8.1	11.6	14.8	19.3	23.3	25.8	25.8	21.1	16.9	12.3	7.7
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Global radiation - horizontal in kWh/m²

1,554	54	74	122	144	190	216	219	193	137	103	57	45
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Position of sun - altitude in °

15.0	6.9	9.6	13.8	18.6	22.6	24.4	23.5	20.2	15.5	10.9	7.5	6.1
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Position of sun - azimuth in °

2.0	0.9	0.5	0.9	2.0	2.6	1.9	1.2	1.5	2.6	3.9	4.0	2.6
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Wind speed in m/s

2.1	2.1	2.5	2.5	2.2	2.0	2.0	2.1	2.0	1.9	1.7	1.9	1.9
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Year	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
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Hot water consumption

DHW heating energy supply in kWh

62,635	6,282	5,784	5,798	5,441	4,808	4,516	4,023	4,446	4,401	5,164	5,782	6,189
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DHW heating energy requirement in kWh

62,743	6,322	5,796	5,798	5,441	4,808	4,516	4,023	4,446	4,401	5,164	5,793	6,234
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Circulation losses in kWh

0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
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Cold water temperature in °C

16.3	13.8	13.5	14.0	15.0	16.4	17.7	18.7	19.0	18.5	17.5	16.1	14.8
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DHW temperature in °C

49.9	49.8	49.9	49.9	49.8	49.9	50.0	50.0	50.0	49.9	49.9	49.8	49.7
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Preset DHW consumption in m³

1,593.8	150.4	136.9	138.5	133.8	123.1	120.4	110.6	123.4	120.4	136.8	147.2	152.4
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DHW - consumption in m³

1,436.8	143.3	130.0	130.6	125.5	111.0	102.3	78.6	96.0	107.5	127.8	139.1	145.1
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Solar loop

Max collector temperature in °C

40.0	24.9	28.5	35.3	38.4	46.3	52.6	58.4	54.8	45.9	39.5	30.2	24.5
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Collector loop

Energy from collector loop (CL 1) in kWh

40,782	1,882	2,394	3,622	3,653	4,336	4,730	4,411	4,682	3,917	3,494	2,125	1,535
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Collector loop efficiency (CL 1) in %

50.2	48.3	50.9	51.7	51.2	50.1	49.9	45.1	50.0	52.5	53.6	51.8	47.9
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Collector loop reference temperature (CL 1) in °C

25.8	17.4	18.4	21.2	23.4	28.3	32.8	40.3	35.8	28.8	24.6	20.2	17.7
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Collector loop outlet temperature (CL 1) in °C

37.6	28.0	30.1	32.8	33.7	37.8	41.3	49.3	44.8	39.1	35.0	30.8	28.0
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Greenforce_Building 3

Year	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
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Volume flow (CL 1) in m³

5,509.2	319.8	353.9	474.4	501.5	565.8	587.6	568.1	571.7	485.0	457.1	343.7	280.7
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Collector array

spec. DNI (CL 1) in kWh/m²

0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
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G opt. loss deduct. (CL 1) in kWh/m²

1,310.8	61.6	74.9	112.4	114.7	139.6	154.0	159.6	153.6	121.0	104.3	64.6	50.4
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Specific global radiation onto inclined surface area (CL 1) in kWh/m²

1,745.0	83.6	101.0	150.3	153.0	185.8	203.4	210.1	200.8	160.2	139.9	88.0	68.8
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Spec. global radiation onto inclined, shaded surface (CL 1) in kWh/m²

1,745.0	83.6	101.0	150.3	153.0	185.8	203.4	210.1	200.8	160.2	139.9	88.0	68.8
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Irradiation on gross surface area -unshaded- (CL 1) in kWh

87,597	4,197	5,073	7,543	7,680	9,325	10,211	10,546	10,082	8,041	7,025	4,419	3,455
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Irradiation on gross surface area (CL 1) in kWh

87,597	4,197	5,073	7,543	7,680	9,325	10,211	10,546	10,082	8,041	7,025	4,419	3,455
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Irradiation on active solar surface area -unshaded- (CL 1) in kWh

81,315	3,896	4,709	7,002	7,130	8,656	9,479	9,790	9,359	7,465	6,522	4,102	3,207
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Irradiation on active surface area (CL 1) in kWh

81,315	3,896	4,709	7,002	7,130	8,656	9,479	9,790	9,359	7,465	6,522	4,102	3,207
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Optical losses (CL 1) in kWh

20,230	1,026	1,219	1,762	1,783	2,149	2,305	2,350	2,202	1,826	1,659	1,092	857
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Losses - external piping (CL 1) in kWh

112	6	7	9	10	12	13	15	12	9	8	6	5
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Losses - internal piping (CL 1) in kWh

324	7	10	18	23	36	47	61	53	33	22	10	6
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Thermal collector losses (CL 1) in kWh

19,867	975	1,079	1,589	1,662	2,123	2,384	2,952	2,410	1,681	1,339	870	804
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Collector outlet temperature (CL 1) in °C

26.5	13.4	16.3	21.9	25.7	31.9	37.3	41.8	39.3	31.6	25.7	18.6	13.3
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-Studio Archimed Shpk

-Tirana, Albania

Greenforce_Building 3

Year	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
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Collector temperature (CL 1) in °C

25.3	12.8	15.4	20.7	24.4	30.5	35.7	40.3	37.8	30.3	24.6	17.9	12.8
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Max collector temperature (CL 1) in °C

37.7	23.3	26.5	32.9	36.0	43.7	49.8	55.7	52.4	43.4	36.6	28.1	22.8
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Pump energy (CL 1) in kWh

1,377	80	88	119	125	141	147	142	143	121	114	86	70
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DHW standby tank

Tank losses in kWh

1,914	138	128	149	147	166	175	222	199	163	152	138	137
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Change in internal energy in kWh

5	3	-4	5	2	-10	28	-1	7	-32	-4	11	0
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Average temperature in °C

53.0	49.6	50.1	50.6	51.1	52.8	55.4	63.2	58.8	53.2	50.9	50.2	49.6
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Auxiliary heating sensor on in °C

53.3	50.0	50.6	51.3	51.6	53.2	55.5	63.2	58.9	53.5	51.5	50.5	49.8
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Sensor: auxiliary heating off in °C

53.3	50.0	50.6	51.3	51.6	53.2	55.5	63.2	58.9	53.5	51.5	50.5	49.8
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E-Electric heater rod in kWh

0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
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Consumption Natural gas (H) in m³

0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
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Desired temperature auxiliary heating in °C

50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0
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Solar preheating tank

Tank losses (S) in kWh

825	-5	7	38	50	97	128	187	155	99	59	15	-5
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Change in internal energy (S) in kWh

-7	-1	22	-18	14	11	48	3	6	-61	-7	-19	-5
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Greenforce_Building 3

Year	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
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Average temperature (S) in °C

31.1	19.2	21.0	25.9	28.1	35.3	41.0	50.5	44.7	36.1	29.0	22.2	19.1
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Sensor: collector loop reference temperature (S) in °C

25.7	17.3	18.4	21.2	23.3	28.2	32.7	40.1	35.7	28.7	24.5	20.1	17.7
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Sensor: collector loop switch-off temperature (S) in °C

40.3	23.9	27.5	36.0	37.2	46.1	53.3	64.2	57.8	47.9	38.7	27.5	22.3
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Consumption Natural gas (H) in m³

0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
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Desired temperature auxiliary heating (S) in °C

0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
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Heat pump

Energy from boiler in kWh

24,590	4,536	3,542	2,351	2,001	737	166	23	130	653	1,870	3,802	4,780
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Primary energy equivalent in kWh

9,836	1,814	1,417	940	801	295	66	9	52	261	748	1,521	1,912
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Consumption Electricity in kWh

Return temperature in °C

57.0	55.4	56.6	58.8	58.5	60.1	60.9	61.3	60.5	60.2	59.4	56.5	55.2
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Supply temperature in °C

59.0	57.4	58.7	60.9	60.6	62.1	62.8	63.0	62.4	62.2	61.4	58.6	57.2
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